

**Modelling and Optimization of
Complex Communication Networks by
Polychromatic Sets Theory**

by

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in the

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Declaration of Authorship

I, Dong Wang, declare that this thesis titled, ‘Modelling and Optimization of Complex Communication Networks by Polychromatic Sets Theory’ and the work presented in it are my own. I confirm that:

- This work was done wholly or mainly while in candidature for a research degree at this University.
- Where any part of this thesis has previously been submitted for a degree or any other qualification at this University or any other institution, this has been clearly stated.
- Where I have consulted the published work of others, this is always clearly attributed.
- Where I have quoted from the work of others, the source is always given. With the exception of such quotations, this thesis is entirely my own work.
- I have acknowledged all main sources of help.
- Where the thesis is based on work done by myself jointly with others, I have made clear exactly what was done by others and what I have contributed myself.

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Abstract

With the development of modern communication technology, wireless communication network has become more complex in the heterogeneous application scenes. Various types of wireless communication nodes join the network and form a complex heterogeneous network for a variety of services and applications, like mobile communications, the Internet of things and so on. Therefore, a novel model is required to re-construct the next generation of communication networks. In this thesis, the Polychromatic Sets (PSets) theory has been proposed and applied to the modelling and optimization of such complex communication networks. PSets is a theory based on traditional graph theory and set theory. It collects multiple properties, like throughput, delay, jitter, energy consumption, and then models the networks followed by a fast route selection algorithm to choose the best links in the complex networks quickly and effectively. Application of the PSets theory has been extended and applied to the scenarios of ultra-reliable low-latency communication (uRLLC) in 5G & beyond airborne networks, the dynamic heterogeneous routing protocol in the Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs), and the service-oriented routing in the Internet of things (IoT).

uRLLC is one of the most significant requirements for future mobile networks. The conventional terrestrial base stations cannot always provide the required uRLLC for emerging applications, like the scenes of large scale temporary events, temporary and urgent applications in the wild area. Therefore, multi-layer airborne networks can be deployed as an effective solution to offer capacity and coverage along with required latency and reliability. With the PSets-based optimized link selection algorithm, multiple properties of the airborne platforms are exploited, and the links are selected based on the multi-constrained requirements to support the desired performance of the airborne network. Moreover, two links distribution schemes have been proposed as distributed greedy scheme and centralized greedy scheme to demonstrate the deployment of the proposed airborne network. Numerical results show that

both PSets-based links distribution schemes outperform the general distribution schemes on average latency and unassociated ratio, which strongly supports the uRLLC in considered airborne networks.

Besides the 5G mobile applications, the heterogeneous architecture of WSNs has become an area of increased research interest in recent years. Such networks comprise a number of wireless nodes of varying capabilities that employ different wireless protocols. The requirements of different applications may vary across different network contexts. Therefore, the new routing schemes are required to dynamically adapt to multiple application requirements and avoid bottlenecked nodes, like low residual energy. PSets-based multi-constrained dynamic routing protocol has been proposed to focus on the optimization of large scale heterogeneous WSNs with hundreds of wireless nodes. Simulation data shows that this protocol predominantly selects high priority nodes for routing, whilst also reducing the use of low priority nodes within the network. In so doing, the proposed method significantly increases overall network performance.

Moreover, IoT is being developed rapidly and applied widely in our society. In this thesis, a PSets-based service oriented routing protocol with cross-layer optimization has been proposed based on the multiple layer properties of IoT. The network performance could be balanced on multiple metrics based on the different requirements of application, like interactive, bulk, real-time, narrow-band, and so on. The simulation results prove that the scheme is effectively able to improve the performance of network when considering multiple network metrics.

Above all, sets of numerical simulations and comparative results show that the PSets theory has been successfully able to optimize the performance of complex networks effectively in these application scenarios. It will be a potential tool to model the next generation of complex communication networks, including the 5G and IoT.

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Abbreviations

5G	the fifth G eneration cellular network technology
AI	A rtificial I ntelligence
AODV	A d hoc O n- demand D istance V ector routing
B5G	B eyond 5G
eMBB	E nhance M obile B roadband
FSO	F ree S pace O ptics
IoT	I nterent of T hings
ITU	I nternational T elecommunication U nion
mMTC	M assive M achine T ype of C ommunication
NGMN	N ext G eneration M obile N etworks A lliance
PSets	P olychromatic S ets
PMFRS	P Sets-based M ulti-constraint F ast R outing S election A lgorithm
QoS	Q uality of S ervice
RF	R adio F requency
SLA	S ervice L evel A greement
SOA	S ervice O riented A rchitecture
SVM	S upport V ector M achine
TTL	T ime to L ive
uRLLC	U ltra R eliable & L ow L atency C ommunication
WBA	W ireless B roadband A lliance
WSNs	W ireless S ensor N etworks

Symbols

G_T	A basic network described by graph theory
$V(G_T)$	A nonempty set of vertices
$E(G_T)$	A set of edges joining the elements in $V(G_T)$
I_{G_T}	Describes the relationship between $E(G_T)$ and $V(G_T)$
a_i	A node
A	The set of all the nodes in a network
n_A	The number of node groups
f	An individual colour
F	A set of all the properties in a network
$F(a)$	An individual colour set
$[A \times F(a)]$	A matrix of collected nodes' individual colours
$F(A)$	A set of some common properties belonging to all the nodes
$G(F_{n_F})$	A property group
n_F	The number of property groups
$[A \times F(A)]$	A matrix consisting of the nodes' unified colours
A_k	A set including two or more nodes on a route
$[A_k \times F(A_k)]$	An all-ones matrix that nodes in set A_{ki} have all the selected properties $F(A_k) = \{F_1, \dots, F_m, \dots, F_n\}$
$A(F)$	The set of all the available routes
$[A \times A(F)]$	A matrix of the link nodes and the corresponding properties

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

5G+AIoT, which is short for 5G, IoT and Artificial Intelligence for IoT, is the most popular topic in wireless communication of current society [1].

5G is the next generation of mobile communication technology. It defines three sets of use cases [2]. The most traditional case is eMBB (Enhance Mobile Broadband) and it has been the first commercial services to launch since 2019 in the UK [3] to match the requirement of high bandwidth for personal users. The second case is mMTC (Massive Machine Type of Communication) and it suits for the large scale application of traditional IoT. The third case, uRLLC (Ultra Reliable & Low Latency Communication), focuses on the special application of ultra-high reliability and low latency. Both of the mMTC and uRLLC have not been in commercial services, and there are still so many challenges on the researches and developments of the two cases, like sliding, service level agreement (SLA) and so on. Meantime, base on these applications, different nodes and elements are integrated to form a typical complex

network. The optimization problem for the future networks which provide the internet for everything is more serious.

uRLLC is one of the most challenging requirements in the application of 5G, and it is also the most difficult one of the three use cases [4]. uRLLC is developed to support several high-ranking services with the latency lower than 10ms [4], for example, the automatic factory, unmanned driving, industry internet and robotic surgery. The low latency networks require to transmit a large number of data with extra low latency. The networks are also required to be ultra reliability, so it should be able to suit the dynamic change of data. uRLLC is integrated with traditional mobile communications, but its Quality of Service (QoS) is completely different from the mobile broadband service. Currently, several basic research outputs have been done based on short code, multiple channels and so on. However, some other breakthrough approaches are still expected to achieve the function.

mMTC is an important characteristic of the 5G revolution, which mainly focuses on the application of large scale IoT. Before the typical mMTC of 5G is promoted, the traditional IoT is mainly developed by the devices working on free license protocols, like Wi-Fi, Bluetooth and ZigBee. All of the three protocols can be deployed on ad-hoc mode [5]. The NGMN (Next Generation Mobile Networks Alliance) and WBA (Wireless Broadband Alliance) also focus on the combination of 5G and Wi-Fi networks [6]. Therefore, 5G and traditional IoT will still coexist in the future. The combination and optimization of mobile networks and traditional IoT based on free license protocols is a challenging problem having not been solved as so far. It is also required to satisfy the service of IoT. Meantime, a large amount of application data and network performance data generates in the IoT with a large number of communication nodes. These data can be used to analyse and optimize the performance of networks by AI.

Therefore, it is valuable to discuss and study the problem of routing optimization in the next generation complex heterogeneous communication networks.

1.2 The problems

In this thesis, several problems related to the routing optimization of complex heterogeneous communication networks are discussed under the scene of 5G and beyond communications.

Complex Networks: The current heterogeneous communication networks are more and more complex due to the attendance of multiple different types of wireless nodes. These wireless nodes have different bandwidth, energy consumption, delay, jitter and other metrics of performance. The different services in the transmission of networks also require different bandwidth, delay and reliability. Therefore, new network models are expected for the application and optimization of the complex communication networks in the future which considering multiple metrics.

uRLLC: The latency and reliability are rigorous requirements in uRLLC networks. Several strategies have been proposed to support uRLLC in underlying communication protocols, for example, using short codes, a high priority in hybrid communications with eMMB, multi-broadcast communications, and unauthorized uplink. However, there are still not so many works having been done in the research of routing discovery and complex communications for uRLLC. Therefore, it is required to support uRLLC with the available links discovered by the optimized routing schemes.

Hybrid Application in IoT: IoT is popularly applied in current society and it is possible to support multiple different applications. Meantime, the

traditional wireless sensor networks operating on unauthorized license protocols and the 4G/5G mobile networks are converging, and a larger scale IoT is formed and applied. Therefore, the optimization of network topology and network service is a more serious problem in the large scale heterogeneous IoT. The new multiple properties aware routing protocols are required to support the optimization of network topology and performance in large scale complex networks. The cross-layer optimization of networks is required to support different communication services in the service-oriented IoT.

Further Optimization by Machine Learning: For complex communication networks, machine learning algorithms are possible to find the features of networks by data mining and knowledge learning. And then it is possible to optimize the networks by analysing and optimizing the network features. It is considered as a significant characteristic of the mobile networks evolving from 5G to 6G via 5.5G. In the large scale complex heterogeneous communication networks, a large amount of data related to the performance of networks is generated. Therefore, it is possible to collect the data to analyse by suitable machine learning algorithms and then optimize the performance of networks.

1.3 Challenges

The challenges of complex communication network applications under the background of 5G+AIoT mainly include two parts:

The Optimized Modelling of Complex Communication Networks: In the current complex communication networks, the different service requirements always change dynamically. However, most of the current researches only propose their ideas to focus on some special networks or a few factors in the networks. As the future networks will always change dynamically to

support the more complex applications, it is difficult to suit the dynamic networks by a static model. Therefore, a common network model is required to support these dynamical networks.

Application of Complex Communication Networks: There are some different optimization targets in the network applications based on their purposes. For example, in the multi-layer airborne networks, how to define the multi-layer networks and also satisfy the essential uRLLC? In the application of large scale IoT, how to optimize the network routing by using the collected performance information of the network nodes to satisfy the dynamic requirements of service? Meantime, in the service-oriented IoT, how to optimize the network routing by cross-layer optimization with the performance information in different layers?

1.4 Contributions and publications

As shown in Figure 1.1, the main contributions of this thesis are discussed below:

Polychrome Sets Theory: In this thesis, the Polychromatic Sets (PSets) theory is first applied in the modelling of complex networks. Based on PSets, the multiple properties of the network nodes and links are collected. It mainly includes bandwidth, latency, jitter, energy consumption and so on. Then, the PSets-based fast link selection algorithm is proposed to find the best links following the required prioritised properties. The method of property discretization and binary arithmetic is discussed. Support Vector Machine (SVM) is applied in the threshold segmentation of property discretization.

uRLLC and the Optimization: A three layers airborne network is proposed to support uRLLC in beyond 5G communication. Two link distribution

FIGURE 1.1: The contributions of the thesis

schemes, which are named as distributed greedy scheme and centralized greedy scheme, are developed in the networks. Meantime, the further optimization of the centralized greedy scheme based on SVM is discussed.

Dynamic Applications of IoT: Two schemes are proposed to focus on the optimization of large-scale WSNs and service-oriented cross-layer optimization of IoT. A PSets-based dynamic geographic routing protocol is proposed to support the dynamic requirements of services in wireless sensor networks for IoT. And then, a virtual network model with cross-layer optimization is proposed based on the performance information of multiple layers in the network to improve the quality of service (QoS) in service-oriented IoT.

The publications of this study are listed below:

Journal Paper:

[1] Dong Wang, Shahriar Abdullah Al-Ahmed, and Muhammad Zeeshan Shakir. “Optimized Link Distribution Schemes for Ultra Reliable and Low Latent Communications in Multi-layer Airborne Networks.” *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, Mar. 2019. (Early Access)

[2] Dong Wang, Muhammad Zeeshan Shakir, Duncan C Thomson, Hong-Hsu Yen, and Charlie Cullen. “A Multi-constrained Dynamic Route Discovery Scheme for Heterogeneous Wireless Sensor Networks.” *IET Wireless Sensor Systems*, May 2019. (Under review)

[3] Dong Wang, Shahriar Abdullah Al-Ahmed, and Muhammad Zeeshan Shakir. “The optimization of uRLLC in Multiple Layers B5G Airborne Networks by Polychromatic Sets and SVM.” *IEEE Communications Letters*. (Under preparation)

Conference Paper:

[4] Dong Wang, Xinheng Wang, Ying Liang, and Zhi Wang. “A Service Oriented Routing Scheme for Internet of Things.” *2017 10th IEEE International Conference on Internet of Things (iThings)*. Exeter, UK, Jun. 2017. pp. 683-688.

[5] Dong Wang, Xinheng Wang, and Hong-Hsu Yen. “A Dynamic Route Discovery Scheme for Heterogeneous Wireless Sensor Networks Based on Polychromatic Sets Theory.” *2016 8th International Conference on Applications of Graph Theory in Wireless Ad hoc Networks and Sensor Networks (GRAPH-HOC)*. Sydney, Australia, Dec. 2016. pp. 103-115.

1.5 Organisation of the thesis

The thesis is organized as follows:

Chapter 1: The introduction of modelling and optimization of complex communication networks is in this chapter. The motivation is introduced in section 1.1. Section 1.2 defines the problems to solve in this thesis, and then

it is followed by the challenges of the problems in section 1.3. Section 1.4 lists the contributions of the thesis.

Chapter 2: The related work is presented in this chapter. Section 2.1 discusses the current research progress on graph theory, set theory and the multi-constraint routing of wireless communications. Section 2.2 introduces the related research on 5G and IoT in recent years.

Chapter 3: The Polychromatic Sets theory and its application in complex communication networks are detailed introduced in this chapter, and two optimized link distribution schemes for ultra reliable and low latent communications in multi-layer airborne networks by PSets are presented in this chapter. Section 3.2 provides the basic definition of PSets-based networks. The routing discovery scheme based on PSets is proposed in subsection 3.2.2. Subsection 3.2.3 discusses the discretization of PSets colours and binary arithmetic and subsection 3.2.4 presents the optimized threshold of PSets colours by SVM. Section 3.3 proposes a three-layer B5G airborne network and then describes the network by PSets. The optimization problem is formulated in section 3.4. Section 3.5 proposes two link distribution schemes, which are named as distributed greedy scheme and centralized greedy scheme. The simulation platform on Matlab is introduced in section 3.6 followed by the simulation results and discussions in section 3.7. Section 3.8 is the summary.

Chapter 4: In this chapter, an optimized routing protocol is proposed to support the large-scale heterogeneous wireless sensor networks working in ad-hoc mode. The network model is defined in Section 4.2 and the routing scheme is proposed in Section 4.3. Section 4.4 provides the simulation and the analysis. It is summarized in Section 4.4.

Chapter 5: In this chapter, an application scene of routing optimization is proposed for the cross-layer routing optimization of service-oriented IoT, a

SOA-based routing scheme is proposed. Similar to Chapter 4, the network model, routing scheme and simulation are presented in three sections, respectively.

Chapter 6: The summary of achievements (section 6.1) and the future research directions (section 6.2) are presented in this chapter.

Appendix A: The core source code of PSets has been published online. The introduce of the main Functions is attached in this appendix.

Chapter 2

Related work

2.1 Graph and multi-constraint

2.1.1 Graph and set theory

Traditional graph theory is not suitable for designing protocols for complex modern networks. New types of graph theories, such as Yao graph [7], finite impulse response graph filters [8] and secrecy graph [9], have been used to develop new protocols. However, even these newly developed graph theories are not fully functional in terms of designing protocols by considering both the properties of the network nodes and links. Limitations of these graph theories are still obvious. Polychromatic graphs based on PSets theory are different from previously developed graphs. PSets theory has the ability to describe multiple properties of a set element, which makes it an ideal tool to consider the properties of both the network nodes and links [10][11]. In the previous works [10] and [11], the basic networks and new routing schemes are described by PSets model. However, the optimized link distribution scheme is

not proposed to focus on multiple properties of the complex networks in the previous papers.

2.1.2 Multi-constraint routing

In recent years, a range of approaches have been proposed for multi-constrained routing protocols. For example, fuzzy logic algorithm is applied in a multi-constraint multicast routing protocol for wireless ad-hoc network [12] and heuristic algorithms is applied in a multi-constrained quality of Service routing [13]. Lagrangian relaxation algorithm [14][15] and polynomial time approximation algorithms [16] are also popular to solve the multi-constraint problems in the networks. A spatial reusability-aware routing [17] is proposed to improve the end-to-end throughput by considering multi-metrics in multi-hop wireless networks and a path observation based physical routing [18] is applied in the wireless ad hoc networks. In the end, a multi-media multi-metric map-aware routing [19] and a multi-metric geographic routing [20] are investigated respectively to applied the geographic information in vehicular ad hoc networks. The aim of the work presented in this thesis is to address this challenge and design a dynamic routing protocol supporting multiple application requirements in a more convenient and easily accessible way.

2.2 5G and IoT

2.2.1 uRLLC in 5G

The exponential growth of human-centric communication services (e.g., smartphones and their complex applications) as well as machine based services (e.g., autonomous vehicles) causing many challenges to the wireless communication

system concerning capacity, latency, reliability, scalability, and energy efficiency [2]. To face the puzzling challenges of the diverse and complicated environment, International Telecommunication Union (ITU) has defined three primary services for the 5G wireless communication system, namely: enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB), massive machine type communication (mMTC) and ultra reliable and low latency communication (uRLLC) [21].

uRLLC is a new and challenging requirement among the three categories which has two conflicting specifications, namely, super low latency and ultra high reliability. One of the typical examples of uRLLC application is Tactile Internet services which have been developed rapidly in recent years [22]. Tactile Internet service is a human-machine collaboration that enables people to control the objects remotely in real time [22]. Many applications have been proposed in the Tactile Internet services, such as immersive virtual reality, Internet of flying platforms, industry automation, tele-surgery and so on [22], [23]. uRLLC is considered as extremely crucial for these type of applications. Identically, uRLLC is equally essential for networks which are deployed during unexpected scenarios, such as in emergencies to support disaster relief activities. The standard requirement of uRLLC is that the latency should be lower than $10ms$ and the reliability should be better than 99.999% [23], [24]. As a result, there are challenges in the link layer, network layer, and physical layer [2]. For example, if we look at the physical layer, reducing the end-to-end latency mandates the use of short packets which affects the channel coding gain. Again to intensify the reliability requires extra resources (e.g., parity check, redundancy, and re-transmissions) which increases the latency [2]. Having said that the current solutions would suffer to satisfy the demand of uRLLC along with capacity and coverage, especially when many users are connected during disaster and sports or cultural events. Moreover, operators will require additional infrastructure to facilitate such emerging applications

and scenarios. However, this approach is going to be very time consuming and expensive [25]. Hence, a new flexible solution is urgently required to support uRLLC for the cellular networks.

Being motivated by the above interesting applications and scenarios, some research and current works are investigated to justify the proposed solution and their limitations. A cross-layer optimization framework has been proposed in [26] to balance up the power allocation and quality of service (QoS). The paper shows that the energy consumption decreases when matching the basic QoS requirements including latency. However, it does not discuss the issue of reducing the latency. An interface diversity scheme for uRLLC has been proposed in [27] and [4]. In this scheme, multiple different interfaces have been applied to transmit the duplicate short packets to increase the reliability and decrease the latency, but the method to extend the interfaces has not been discussed. In [28] and [29], the authors proposed a system level protocol to optimize uRLLC. Several joint scheduling schemes to support uRLLC and eMBB have been proposed in [30], [31] and [32] based on different ideas. Paper [30] proposes a channel shared scheme, minislots are applied in paper [31] and a null-space-based spatial preemptive scheduler is introduced in paper [32].

Recently, the airborne networks have been introduced as a key architectural enabler for beyond 5G (B5G) networks [33]. Many schemes have been proposed to support different applications and scenarios in future airborne networks. In [34], an optimal resource allocation scheme has been proposed to minimize the packet delay in multi-layer airborne networks. The authors in [25] have provided an optimized delay scheme using flying platforms. The reliability and flexibility of flying platforms assisted networks have been discussed in [35]. The authors in [36], [37] and [38] have proposed solutions to improve spectrum and energy efficiency of flying platform aided cellular networks. In

[39], the authors have discussed the deployment of flying platforms based on user demand, in particular, during high traffic demand scenarios.

Despite having all these current research on uRLLC and airborne networks, there is no related paper has been published to support the uRLLC by the airborne networks as so far.

2.2.2 WSNs and IoT

Normally, for WSNs, energy consumption [40] and QoS based routing [41] are two major concerns. Multi-constrained QoS routing [41] is a hot topic, with much research ongoing. Ben-Othman et al. proposed an energy-efficient and QoS-aware multi-path routing protocol for WSNs [42]. Yao et al. provided an energy-efficient, delay-aware and lifetime-balanced data collection scheme [43]. Singal et al. introduced a QoS-aware routing based on a multi-constraints link stability cost function [44]. However, even for multi-constrained QoS routing, the parameters used for designing routing protocols are predefined and, therefore, it is difficult to adapt to the dynamic nature of modern heterogeneous wireless networks.

Many work has been contributed on SOA for wireless networks. The main idea of these work is to add a service layer between the application layer and network layer, and then manage the network by a software defined middleware [45][46]. In [45] an adaptable and flexible middleware was proposed to configure the functionalities of wireless networks. An extensible and scalable SOA was proposed in [46] to deploy the network management system for large scale heterogeneous networks. All of these methods integrate the interconnection between application layer and network layer effectively, and then the network

layer is able to acquire the service requirements from application layer. However, all of these work only redefines the network structure, but no routing scenario is proposed and deployed.

Large scale IoT systems are a typical heterogeneous network. In a heterogeneous network, the same node would ask the network to provide different performance based on different services. Some work in [47][48] proposed their SOA-based different paths selection algorithms for heterogeneous networks. Authors in [47] proposed an algorithm for Service Path Selection and Adaptation. Two service-oriented routing models were proposed in [48]. One is named as Cost Based Model and the cost of network is considered, the other is named as Gain Based Model and the relative value of service is considered. These papers provide the routing scenarios for their special applications. However, these scenarios do not provide a variable routing scheme to match multiple different applications in the same networks.

Network virtualization is a significant method to build the service oriented networks. It is possible to separate the network services and physical networks by using virtual networks, and then provide the optimized services based on network requirements [49]. Authors in [49] described the method and target of network virtualization, respectively. Different virtual network structures are defined and analyzed in these papers. However, their work did not explain the mathematical definitions and applications of virtual networks in detail, and did not provide the detailed scenario on operation either.

In some research work, only one attribute of the network is considered as a routing metric, for example, energy aware in [50]. In addition, some other research considers multiple metrics of network, for example, multiple metrics of networks are defined in detail in [51]. Psets theory is supposed to be a promising technique to consider multiple metrics of the network and thus

improve the network performance. dynamic multiple metrics aware routing protocol was proposed and applied in heterogeneous wireless sensor networks. However, the detailed definition and analysis of network nodes have not been done yet.

Chapter 3

uRLLC in 5G & beyond airborne networks

3.1 Introduction

Ultra reliable and low latency communications (uRLLC) is one of the most significant requirements for future 5G and beyond networks. The conventional terrestrial base stations cannot always provide the required uRLLC for emerging applications and scenarios, e.g., Tactile Internet services or when a large number of users get connected during an event. Therefore, multi-layer airborne networks with low/medium/high altitude platforms can be deployed as an effective solution to offer capacity and coverage along with required latency and reliability for wireless networks.

The airborne network can be considered as a potential solution to provide capacity, coverage, reliability and low latency [33]. Such airborne networks are capable of building a flexible, temporary network to increase the links and bandwidth for advanced requirements. In addition, the signal-to-noise ratio

of user-to-air links is better than traditional ground links which decrease with the interference in some situation [52]. Above all, the airborne networks could be deployed in the temporary people-intensive places, such as in a stadium or during a disaster. In this way, it is possible to decrease the costly deployment of the base station (BS) and associated infrastructure for temporary events. Likewise, the airborne networks could be deployed quickly to support the rescue operations during an earthquake or other natural disasters where the BS and associated infrastructure gets destroyed.

In this chapter, three layers of the airborne network to support the uRLLC requirement in wireless networks is proposed with the aid of Polychromatic Sets theory (PSets). Optimized link selection schemes have been provided based on PSets theory to focus on the uRLLC. PSets is an optimization model for the analysis of the complex network [10]. Several previous works have been done on network optimization. In this work, we have applied PSets on the airborne network. The PSets model is simple and efficient in contrast with the other network optimization tools [10]. With the optimized link selection algorithm, multiple properties of the airborne platforms are exploited, and the links are selected based on the multi-constrained requirements to support the desired performance of the airborne network. Moreover, two links distribution schemes have been proposed as distributed greedy scheme and centralized greedy scheme to demonstrate the deployment of the proposed airborne network. Numerical results show that both PSets-based links distribution schemes outperform the general distribution schemes on average latency and overall reliability also known as the unassociated ratio, which strongly supports the uRLLC in considered airborne networks.

The proposed three layers airborne network has three types of flying platforms with different performance including different roles. It is expected to provide flexible deployment and support the temporary requirements of

uRLLC. In the multiple layer airborne network, the flying platforms could join in the network with different performance, so it forms a heterogeneous network. In the proposed network, it is important to measure the performance of each link and then choose the best link for end-to-end connection from the lower layer to the higher layer via medium layer to offer uRLLC for the networks. Thus, we first propose the multiple property aware link selection based on PSets and then later, we propose two optimized link distribution schemes to support the uRLLC. The distributed greedy scheme focuses on the requirement of each connection in a decentralized network. On the contrary, the centralized greedy scheme focuses on the centralized network. Both schemes provide better performance than traditional schemes without considering the influence of the performance of different flying platforms.

3.2 Polychromatic Sets Theory

Graph theory is a mathematical method to model, analyze and develop network protocols. A basic network consists of nodes and links, and is described by graph theory [53] as $G_T = (V(G_T), E(G_T), I_{G_T})$, where $V(G_T)$ is a nonempty set of vertices, $E(G_T)$ is a set of edges joining the elements in $V(G_T)$, and I_{G_T} describes the relationship between $E(G_T)$ and $V(G_T)$. In traditional graph theory, only the nodes and links of the network are described, and many properties of the node and link are discarded.

In contrast with traditional graph theory, PSets [54] include not only all of the basic elements of a graph but also the properties of these elements. PSets are a group of sets that represent the nodes, the names of node properties, the node properties themselves, and the links.

In this section, the PSets theory and its application in complex networks are detailedly introduced. Firstly, the PSets-based definition of networks is provided in section 3.2. A routing discovery algorithm is proposed based on PSets in section 3.3. Section 3.4 discusses the discretization of continuous parameters and the optimization of large-scale computing by computer. Section 3.5 introduces the optimization of continuous parameters discretization based on Support Vector Machine (SVM). A summary is in section 3.6.

3.2.1 PSets-based network definition

To describe the theory, Figure 3.1 illustrates an example network which includes seven wireless nodes, divided into two clusters, $\{a_1, a_2, a_3\}$ and $\{a_4, a_5, a_6, a_7\}$. These nodes connect with each other and transmit packets in their signal cover area. In this network, multiple metrics of the nodes and links are considered, such as location, energy, bandwidth, signal quality.

FIGURE 3.1: An example of network with seven nodes in two groups

3.2.1.1 Nodes set A

The set of all the nodes in a network is defined as set A , which is described as $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_i, \dots, a_p\}$, where a_i is node i in set A . It is similar to the vertices set in traditional graph. The number of nodes is p . Nodes are classified into several groups (where the classification method depends on the problem), defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_1 &= \{a_1, \dots, a_i\}, \\
 A_2 &= \{a_{i+1}, \dots, a_{i+j}\}, \\
 &\dots \\
 A_{n_A} &= \{a_{i+j+\dots+1}, \dots, a_p\}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.1}$$

where n_A is the number of groups. In the communication networks, the groups are normally classified based on the role of nodes to find the appropriate links.

3.2.1.2 Properties (colours)

In PSets theory, the properties are named *colours*. F is a set of all the properties in a network, including node properties and link properties. However, in order to simplify arithmetic calculations, the link properties are always converted to node properties. If there is a link between two nodes, the link is expressed as one node having a property to connect with the other node. For example, the length of a link is converted to the location of the two nodes connected by the link.

3.2.1.3 Individual colour

$F(a)$ is a set of all the properties belonging to one node, named an individual colour set. It is described as $F(a) = \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_j, \dots, f_q\}$, where f is an individual colour and q is the number of individual colours.

A number of nodes' individual colours are collected together and displayed as a matrix:

$$[A \times F(a)] = \begin{matrix} & f_1 & \cdots & f_j & \cdots & f_q & \\ \begin{matrix} a_1 \\ \cdots \\ a_i \\ \cdots \\ a_p \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} c_{11} & \cdots & c_{1j} & \cdots & c_{1q} \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \\ c_{i1} & \cdots & c_{ij} & \cdots & c_{iq} \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \\ c_{p1} & \cdots & c_{pj} & \cdots & c_{pq} \end{bmatrix} & \end{matrix} \quad (3.2)$$

$$c_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, f_j \in F(a_i) \\ 0 \end{cases}$$

If one node a_i is coloured f_j , then the element c_{ij} in the above matrix is set as 1, otherwise, it is 0.

3.2.1.4 Unified colour

$F(A)$ is a set of some common properties belonging to all the nodes in a network, which is also named as a unified colour, which is defined as:

$$\begin{cases} F(A) = \{F_1, F_2, \dots, F_j, \dots, F_q\} \\ F(A) \subset F(a) \end{cases} \quad (3.3)$$

In a network, the unified colour of $F(A)$ is a subset of these nodes' individual colours $F(a)$. As for nodes, the properties are divided into several groups, depending on the problem, as:

$$\begin{aligned}
G(F_1) &= \{f_1, \dots, f_m\}, \\
G(F_2) &= \{f_{m+1}, \dots, f_{m+n}\}, \\
&\dots \\
G(F_{n_F}) &= \{f_{m+n+\dots+1}, \dots, f_q\}.
\end{aligned} \tag{3.4}$$

where n_F is the number of groups.

$[A \times F(A)]$ is a matrix consisting of the nodes' unified colours, which is defined as:

$$[A \times F(A)] = \begin{bmatrix} & F_1 & \dots & F_j & \dots & F_q \\ c_{11} & \dots & c_{1j} & \dots & c_{1q} & a_1 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ c_{i1} & \dots & c_{ij} & \dots & c_{iq} & a_i \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ c_{p1} & \dots & c_{pj} & \dots & c_{pq} & a_p \end{bmatrix} \tag{3.5}$$

$$c_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & F_j \in F(A_i) \\ 0 & \end{cases}$$

If one node a_i is coloured F_j , then the element c_{ij} in the above matrix is set as 1, otherwise, it is 0.

3.2.2 Routing discovery based on PSets

With the multiple properties of a network defined by PSets theory, it is straightforward to discover all the available routes by a few arithmetic calculations. Normally, graph theory is utilized to find the best route in a network. PSets allow finding the required routes matching the desired properties among the selected nodes or node groups. For example, in Figure 3.1, all the nodes are divided into two groups. A source node wants to establish a path to a destination node through the two clusters. A connected link is required between the two clusters. In order to increase the performance of the route, the nodes with high performance should be prioritized.

3.2.2.1 Routing discovery solution

Set A_k is defined as a set including two or more nodes, like a_l and a_s , on a route. It is a subset of set A . These nodes have all the selected properties $F(A_k)$ from $F(A)$ in the network, which is defined as:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} A_k = \{a_l, \dots, a_s\} \subset A \\ F(A_k) = \{F_1, \dots, F_m, \dots, F_n\} \subset F(A) \\ [A_k \times F(A_k)] = \begin{array}{c} \begin{array}{cccccc} & & F_1 & \cdots & F_m & \cdots & F_n \\ \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \cdots & 1 & \cdots & 1 \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \\ 1 & \cdots & 1 & \cdots & 1 \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \\ 1 & \cdots & 1 & \cdots & 1 \end{bmatrix} & \begin{array}{l} A_{k1} \\ \cdots \\ A_{ki} \\ \cdots \\ A_{kj} \end{array} \end{array} \end{array} \right. \quad (3.6)$$

$[A_k \times F(A_k)]$ is an all-ones matrix that nodes in set A_{ki} have all the selected properties $F(A_k) = \{F_1, \dots, F_m, \dots, F_n\}$.

The set of all the available routes are described as:

$$A(F) = \{A_{k1}, \dots, A_{ki}, \dots, A_{kj}\} \quad (3.7)$$

All the link nodes and the corresponding properties are displayed in a matrix as:

$$[A \times A(F)] = \begin{matrix} & F(A_{k1}) & \cdots & F(A_{kj}) & \cdots & F(A_{kq}) \\ \begin{bmatrix} c_{11} & \cdots & c_{1j} & \cdots & c_{1q} \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \\ c_{i1} & \cdots & c_{ij} & \cdots & c_{iq} \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \\ c_{p1} & \cdots & c_{pj} & \cdots & c_{pq} \end{bmatrix} & a_1 \\ & \cdots \\ & a_i \\ & \cdots \\ & a_p \end{matrix} \quad (3.8)$$

$$c_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, a_i \in A_{kj} \\ 0 \end{cases}$$

Specifically, we divide (3.8) into two parts and define:

$$[A \times A(F)'] = \begin{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} c_{11} & \cdots & c_{1j} & \cdots & c_{1q} \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \\ c_{i1} & \cdots & c_{ij} & \cdots & c_{iq} \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \\ c_{p1} & \cdots & c_{pj} & \cdots & c_{pq} \end{bmatrix} & a_1 \\ & \cdots \\ & a_i \\ & \cdots \\ & a_p \end{matrix} \quad (3.9)$$

$$c_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, a_i \in A_{kj} \\ 0 \end{cases}$$

and

$$F(A_k)' = \{F(A_{k1}), \dots, F(A_{ki}), \dots, F(A_{kj})\} \quad (3.10)$$

where $F(A_k)'$ is a set of selected properties, $[A \times A(F)']$ is a matrix recording whether the node a_i belongs to set A_{kj} and has all the properties in $F(A_{kj})$ or not.

A common model is developed to acquire the set of selected links $[A \times A(F)]$ from the set of nodes' unified colours $[A \times F(A)]$. The conjunction of different nodes' properties $[F \times F(A)]$ is displayed as:

$$\begin{aligned} [F \times F(A)] &= [F_m \times A(F_m)] \wedge [F_n \times A(F_n)] \wedge \dots \wedge [F_l \times A(F_l)] \\ & \text{s.t.} \\ \forall A_{ijk} &= \{a_i, a_j, \dots, a_k\} \in [A \times A(F)'], \\ F(A_{ijk}) &= \{F_m, F_n, \dots, F_l\} \in F(A_k)': \\ F_{mnl}(a_i) \wedge F_{mnl}(a_j) \wedge \dots \wedge F_{mnl}(a_k) &= 1 \end{aligned} \quad (3.11)$$

where $[F_m \times A(F_m)]$ is a rank of node's properties F_m , A_{ijk} is a set of nodes matching the required properties, $F(A_{ijk})$ is the set of properties which the nodes in A_{ijk} match and $F_{mnl}(a_i)$ is the tag whether a_i has all the properties F_{mnl} or not.

Algorithm 3.1 can be used to find the available paths in $[A \times A(F)]$. In Algorithm 3.1, $[F \times F(A)]$ is the conjunction of different nodes' properties, $[F_m \times A(F_m)]$ is a rank of node's properties, F_m and $F_{mnl}(a_i)$ are the tags whether a_i has all the properties F_{mnl} or not. Based on this algorithm, seven parameters are required for input: a set of nodes A_f , a set of colours F_f , a set of nodes' properties $[A_f \times F_f]$, number of node groups n_A , node groups A_1, \dots, A_{n_A} , number of property groups n_F and property groups G_1, \dots, G_{n_F} .

The set of selected nodes $[A \times A(F)']$ and the parallel set of their matching properties $F(A_k)'$ are output.

Algorithm 3.1 : $[A_f \times F_f] \longrightarrow [A \times A(F)]$

Input: $A_f, F_f, [A_f \times F_f], n_A, A_1, \dots, A_{n_A}, n_F, G_1, \dots, G_{n_F}$
Output: $[A \times A(F)'], F(A_k)'$

- 1: initialization;
- 2: **for** $m = 1 : size(G_1)$
- 3: **for** $n = 1 : size(G_2)$
- 4: \dots %total : n_F
- 5: **for** $l = 1 : size(G_{n_F})$
- 6: $[F \times F(A)] = [F_m \times A(F_m)] \wedge [F_n \times A(F_n)] \wedge \dots \wedge [F_l \times A(F_l)];$
 %total : n_F
- 7: **if** $F_{mnl}(a_i) \wedge F_{mnl}(a_j) \wedge \dots \wedge F_{mnl}(a_k) == 1$ %total : n_A
- 8: $[A \times A(F)'] \Leftarrow \{a_i, a_j, \dots, a_k\};$ %total : n_A
- 9: $F(A_k)' \Leftarrow F_m, F_n, \dots, F_l;$ %total : n_F
- 10: **end**
- 11: **end**
- 12: \dots %total : n_F
- 13: **end**
- 14: **end**

3.2.2.2 Application of network routes discovery

An example explains the application to the discovery of network routes. The network in Figure 3.1 includes 7 nodes, $a_1 \sim a_7$. These nodes are divided into two groups, as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A &= \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6, a_7\} \\
 A_1 &= \{a_1, a_2, a_3\} \\
 A_2 &= \{a_4, a_5, a_6, a_7\} \\
 n_A &= 2
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.12}$$

For the multiple properties aware network, seven properties are defined. As shown in Table 3.1, these properties belong to 3 groups, namely frequency band, bandwidth and power. Real network properties are used to illustrate likely values.

TABLE 3.1: Properties of the example network

f	F	Property	Nodes
f_1	F_1	Frequency: 2.4GHz	$a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6, a_7$
f_2	F_2	Frequency: 5GHz	a_1, a_5, a_7
f_3	-	Frequency: 60GHz	none
f_4	-	Bandwidth: 54Mbps	$a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6, a_7$
f_5	F_3	Bandwidth: 300Mbps	a_1, a_2, a_4, a_5, a_7
f_6	F_4	Power: Battery	a_2, a_3, a_5, a_7
f_7	F_5	Power: Cable	a_1, a_4, a_6

Each node has its individual properties. The set of nodes' individual colours is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 F(A) &= \{F_1, F_2, F_3, F_4, F_5\} = \{f_1, f_2, f_5, f_6, f_7\} \subset F(a) \\
 G(1) &= \{F_1, F_2\} \\
 G(2) &= \{F_3\} \\
 G(3) &= \{F_4, F_5\} \\
 n_F &= 3
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.13}$$

The matrix of nodes' unified colour is:

$$[A \times F(A)] = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.14)$$

In this example, we assume that only the nodes having all the same properties belonging to each property group can connect with each other. Then following the model in last subsection, $[A \times A(F)]$ ($F(A_k)'$ and $[A \times A(F)']$) are derived and shown in Figure 3.2. Links in the network are shown in Figure 3.3.

FIGURE 3.2: Available links by PSets

As shown in Figure 3.2 and Figure 3.3, three links matching the requirements are selected, (a_2, a_5) , (a_2, a_7) and (a_1, a_4) . The network properties of

FIGURE 3.3: Available links in the network

these links are $\{F_1, F_3, F_4\}$, $\{F_1, F_3, F_4\}$ and $\{F_1, F_3, F_5\}$, respectively. In Figure 3.2, each column record the information of a link. For example, the first column means that there is a link between node a_2 and a_5 following the properties F_1 , F_3 and F_4 .

3.2.2.3 Virtual colours

Based on PSets model, a link is selected only when all the nodes have the required colours. The above example illustrates how PSets theory can be applied in a simple scenario. However, a more typical network is more complex than the above example. There are many different connecting schemes that require the nodes with different colours to connect. For example, we divide the energy consumption and residual energy into several levels, however, the nodes in different energy consumption and residual energy level can connect with other nodes. We choose the nodes with high priority firstly, but the nodes with low priority can also be chosen and used as the next hop node.

Therefore, virtual colour is introduced and utilized for calculating PSets with the connection by nodes having multiple different properties.

Virtual colours are the required colours assigned to a node temporarily when using PSets model. It is defined as:

$$\forall \begin{cases} F_{vA_v} = F_{jA_v} \\ a_i \in A_v \end{cases} : F_v(a_i) = 1_{virtual} \quad (3.15)$$

where F_{vA_v} is the name of virtual colour, F_{jA_v} is the name of required colour and A_v is the required node group. If any node a_i belongs to A_v and the required colour F_{jA_v} has the same name as the virtual colour F_{vA_v} , it adds this colour to the node a_i .

3.2.3 Discretization of PSets colours and binary arithmetic

PSets theory could be used in networks to include multiple network metrics, and it is able to acquire the optimized links matching the requirements by arithmetic. In the previous sections, we defined one metric of network with several parameters. However, some network metrics, like location of nodes and residual energy of nodes, are consecutive value. If we define these properties with only a few parameters, much useful information will be lost. Therefore, we consider the discretization and binary arithmetic of consecutive value for PSets in this section.

The process of discretization and binary arithmetic of consecutive value is shown as: Original Parameter -> Binary -> Save -> Switch and Check -> Arithmetic based on PSets.

FIGURE 3.4: Discretization and binary arithmetic

Original Parameter: The original parameter a of a property could be acquired. For example, if the granularity of residual energy is 1%, the residual energy could be $a\%$. If the granularity of node location is 1m, the location of a node in x -axis, y -axis and z -axis could be (a_x, a_y, a_z) .

Binary: If $2^{n-1} \leq a < 2^n$, it need n bits to save the binary parameter. For example, as $2^6 \leq 100 < 2^7$, 7 bits are used to save 100 parameters of one property. A decimal number could be expressed by a binary number, as $(a)_{10} = (a)_2$. For example, $(53)_{10} = (110101)_2$.

Save: Save the number as a binary number. For example, the number $(53)_{10}$ could be saved as $(110101)_2$.

Switch and Check: There are three situations.

- Matching one parameter: It could be check that whether parameter a match with parameter b by judging if $a == b$ and $\sim a == \sim b$. For example, checking the above number could be done by judging if $0110101 == 0110101$ and $1001010 == 1001010$.
- Matching multiple parameters: It could be check that if parameter a match with multiple parameters b_1, b_2, \dots, b_k by using the method of matching one parameter repeatedly.
- Matching a parameter interval: It could be check that if parameter a belong to interval $p \sim q$. Firstly, it should be switched by $(i)_2 = (a)_2 - (p)_2$ and $(j)_2 = (q)_2 - (p)_2$. Then, check the two binary numbers from the first bit in the left that if $i! = j$ and $i > j$, a do not belong to the interval.

Arithmetic based on PSets: The arithmetic is based on the previous PSets arithmetic.

3.2.4 Optimization of clustering continuous parameters

Set theory (Polychromatic Sets) is essential to model and optimization the networks in complex networks. The sets are able to collect multiple properties of the networks. It is easy to define the properties with discrete parameters, like protocols = {RF, FSO, mm-Wave}. However, the parameters of some other properties are continuous functions (not discrete), like latency.

In the previous sections, we cluster the continuous parameters into several elements of a set, like low, medium and high latency. However, the threshold of the elements is configured by hand. So it is considered to using SVM [55] to configure the threshold and optimize the networks.

Based on SVM, it is also available to configure the new nodes which added to the network and then optimize the network.

The simulation and result will be given in subsection 3.7.3.

3.3 Three-layer B5G airborne network

Application of the flying platform in the current network has become more popular since recently. It would be challenging to maintain networks with an increasing number of flying platforms. Therefore, the multi-layer architecture would be an efficient solution to deploy at no less than three layers based on their common attributes.

3.3.1 Network architecture

FIGURE 3.5: An airborne network with three layers, multiple types of users connected with the core network through various flying platforms.

As shown in Figure 3.5, due to the congestion or damage, the wired links cannot satisfy the requirement of uRLLC. Therefore, a three layers airborne

platform is deployed. The low layer (LL) comprises of low endurance flying platforms that offers connectivity to multiple users to the networks. The medium layer (ML) has medium endurance flying platforms to relay the connections between high layer (HL) and LL/BS. The HL consists of one or a few flying platforms with high endurance which can maintain in the sky for a long duration with sufficient energy and required bandwidth to offer transport network between ML and core networks (CN).

3.3.2 Basic properties of airborne networks

In this work, we consider the deployment of various types of flying platforms to provide connectivity and deliver data packets in the network. For this type of complex network, we describe airborne network properties by PSets.

TABLE 3.2: Multiple properties of airborne networks

Property	Parameter 1	Parameter 2	Parameter 3	Parameter 4
Location	x_L	y_L	z_L	-
Layer	low layer L_L	medium layer L_M	high layer L_H	-
Idle	busy I_B	idle I_I	sleep I_S	-
Latency	low Lt_L	medium Lt_M	high Lt_H	-
Bandwidth	high B_H	medium B_M	low B_L	-
Jitter	low J_L	medium J_M	high J_H	-
Quality	new Q_N	medium Q_M	old Q_O	-
Residual Energy	low E_L	medium E_M	high E_H	extra-high E_E
Protocol	RF P_R	FSO P_F	mm-Wave P_M	-

Based on PSets theory, as many as network properties could be included in the sets. As shown in Table 3.2, the multiple properties of flying platforms in the airborne network are considered such as location, layer, idle, latency, bandwidth, jitter, quality, residual energy, and communication protocol. Flying platforms are associated with the layers in airborne network based on the basic QoS parameters such as their location, idle, latency, bandwidth and

jitter. The performance of flying platforms decreases when they are in operation for a long time. The quality of flying platforms is considered as a comprehensive metric to measure the performance of the hardware.

A battery powers most of the flying platforms and they are limited in energy. Therefore, energy efficiency has been considered as an essential performance metric in such networks. In this work, we consider the residual energy of flying platforms which is denoted by low, medium, high and extra-high as shown in Table 3.2. Flying platforms with extra-high residual energy represent energy harvesting enabled flying platforms with unlimited energy, such as a solar battery.

It is further assumed that the flying platforms in the considered airborne networks are carrying payload (transceivers) with different protocols, like RF, FSO and mm-Wave. In this situation, a flying platform can only connect with another flying platform which operates on the same protocol. As shown in Table 3.2, the availability of the three protocols, RF, FSO and mm-Wave are denoted by P_R , P_F P_M , respectively.

3.3.3 The three layer network defined by PSets

3.3.3.1 Flying platforms

In this work, the flying platforms are categorized into three layers, as A_1 , A_2 and A_3 .

Set A is defined as a set of all the flying platforms in a network, which is described as $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_i, \dots, a_{i+j}, \dots, a_p\}$, where a_i and a_{i+j} are flying platform i and $i + j$ in set A and p is the number of flying platforms. In the

three layers network, flying platforms are classified into three groups, which is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A &= \{A_1, A_2, A_3\}, \\
 A_1 &= \{a_1, \dots, a_i\}, \\
 A_2 &= \{a_{i+1}, \dots, a_{i+j}\}, \\
 A_3 &= \{a_{i+j+1}, \dots, a_p\}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.16}$$

3.3.3.2 Properties of flying platforms

$F(a)$ denotes a set of all the properties belonging to a flying platform, which is also named as an individual colour set. It is described as $F(a) = \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_j, \dots, f_q\}$, where f is an individual colour and q is the number of individual colours.

For example, based on the defined properties in Table 3.2, the set of properties $F(a)$ is defined as $F(a) = \{f_{LL}, f_{LM}, \dots, f_{PM}\}$. It consists of 25 parameters of the properties. However, as so far, based on the current contributions of PSets model, the 3D locations have not been considered as a property in the model.

3.3.3.3 Network

A number of flying platforms' individual colours are collected together and displayed as a matrix:

$$\begin{aligned}
[A \times F(a)] &= \begin{bmatrix} & f_1 & \cdots & f_j & \cdots & f_q \\ c_{11} & \cdots & c_{1j} & \cdots & c_{1q} & a_1 \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \\ c_{i1} & \cdots & c_{ij} & \cdots & c_{iq} & a_i \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \\ c_{p1} & \cdots & c_{pj} & \cdots & c_{pq} & a_p \end{bmatrix} & (3.17) \\
c_{ij} &= \begin{cases} 1, f_j \in F(a_i), \\ 0. \end{cases}
\end{aligned}$$

If a flying platform a_i is coloured f_j , then the element c_{ij} in the above matrix is set as 1, otherwise, it is 0.

3.4 Problem formulation

In the three layers network, the connections are similar between any upper layer flying platforms and lower layer flying platforms. Therefore, we define them as a mother flying platform m_i and associated child flying platforms as $M_L = \{m_{L1}, \dots, m_{Lj}, \dots, m_{Ln_i}\}$, where n_i denotes the number of the child flying platforms associated with a mother flying platform m_i .

Firstly, a link L_{ij} between two flying platforms following the PSets rule is defined as

$$L_{ij} \sim \{(m_i, m_{Lj}) \in [A \times A(F)]\}, \quad (3.18)$$

where if $(m_i, m_{L_j}) \in [A \times A(F)]$ is true, $L_{ij} = 1$. Otherwise, $L_{ij} = 0$. $[A \times A(F)]$ is the set of selected links by PSets model which was introduced in Section 3.2.

Moreover, we assume that the maximal number of links that a mother flying platform could support is n_{Lm_i} , so,

$$\sum_{j=1}^{n_i} L_{ij} \leq n_{Lm_i}. \quad (3.19)$$

The total bandwidth of a mother flying platform is b_i , so,

$$\sum_{j=1}^{n_i} b_{ij} \cdot L_{ij} \leq b_i, \quad (3.20)$$

where b_{ij} is the bandwidth of the link between flying platform m_i and m_{L_j} .

For the considered airborne network, the real-time number of routes in the three layers network is n_r . For a route r_k , it connects an HL flying platform and a LL flying platform via an ML flying platform, so the number of routes hop h_{r_k} is two.

Therefore, the total latency T_{r_k} should lower than the satisfied latency T_s , as

$$\sum_{h=1}^{h_{r_k}} T_{r_k, h} \leq T_s. \quad (3.21)$$

Our objective is to find the lowest total latency of T in a multi-hop link, as

$$\min T = \sum_{k=1}^{n_r} \sum_{h=1}^{h_{r_k}} T_{r_k,h}, \quad (3.22)$$

subject to

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{h=1}^{h_{r_k}} T_{r_k,h} &\leq T_s, \\ \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} L_{ij} &\leq n_{Lm_i}, \\ \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} b_{ij} \cdot L_{ij} &\leq b_i, \\ L_{ij} &\sim \{(m_i, m_{Lj}) \in [A \times A(F)]\}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.23)$$

3.5 Proposed schemes

In this section, two schemes are designed for the distribution of the links to focus on distributed networks and centralized networks, which are: distributed greedy scheme and centralized greedy scheme.

3.5.1 Distributed greedy scheme

The distributed greedy algorithm has been divided into three steps, which is shown in Algorithm 3.2. In the two hops distributed greedy scheme, each flying platform of the lower layer only has the connection information with its mother flying platform in the upper layer. It cannot get and frequently update the connection information of the whole network. Therefore, it is also difficult to update the routing discovery frequently based on the requirement.

Algorithm 3.2 : Distributed greedy scheme

Input: $N_H, N_M, N_L, L_H, L_M, C_{L_{Hmax}}, C_{B_{Hmax}}, C_{L_{Mmax}}, C_{B_{Mmax}}, T_{HM}, T_{ML}, T_{max}, B$

Output: R

- 1: **Step 1:** Get the list of all the available flying platforms connected to the higher layer flying platform;
- 2: **for** $i = 1 : N_H$
- 3: **for** $j = 1 : N_M$
- 4: **if** $L_{Hij} \sim 0$
- 5: $S_{Hi} \leftarrow L_{Hij}$;
- 6: **end if**
- 7: **end for**
- 8: **end for**
- 9: **order** the flying platforms in S by increasing of distance between the flying platforms and their mother flying platform
- 10: **Step 2:** Find the flying platforms focus on the max bandwidth and links;
- 11: Initialize: $C_L = 0, C_B = 0$
- 12: **for** $i = 1 : N_H$
- 13: **for** $j = 1 : N_M$
- 14: **if** $S_{Hij} \sim 0$ and $C_{Li} < C_{Lmax}$ and $C_{Bi} < C_{Bmax}$
- 15: **remove** L_{Hij} from other S_H ;
- 16: $C_{Li+} = 1, C_{Bi+} = B_j$;
- 17: **end if**
- 18: **end for**
- 19: **end for**
- 20: **Step 3:** Find the route based on the associated links;
- 21: **for** $i = 1 : N_H$
- 22: **for** $j = 1 : N_M$
- 23: **for** $k = 1 : N_L$
- 24: **if** exist R_{ijk} and $T_{HMij} + T_{MLjk} < T_{max}$
- 25: $R_i = (S_{Mjk}, S_{Hij})$;
- 26: **end if**
- 27: **end for**
- 28: **end for**
- 29: **end for**

Before starting the algorithm, the basic parameters have been considered as that the number of flying platforms in three layers N_H , N_M and N_L . The lists of all the available links selected by PSets route discovery model are denoted by L_H and L_M . The maximum link numbers of flying platforms in high layer

and medium layer are denoted by C_{LHmax} and C_{LMmax} , respectively. Variables C_{BHmax} and C_{BMmax} denote the maximum bandwidth of flying platforms in high layer and medium layer, respectively. T_{HM} denotes the list of all the links' latency between high and medium layer, and T_{ML} denotes latency list between medium and low layer. The TTL (Time to Live) is denoted by T_{max} . Variable B denotes the bandwidth provided to each link. The result of the final routes is saved as set R .

Step 1: The first step is to find all the available flying platforms connected to their mother flying platform and save them as a list S_{Hj} . For the flying platforms in the medium layer, if a link between the flying platform and its mother flying platform in high layer exist in L_H , the flying platform is saved in the list of its mother flying platform's available links S_{Hj} . In this step, the flying platform could have multiple available mother flying platforms, and the final mother flying platform will be decided in the next step. Then, reorder the flying platforms in the list of each mother flying platform by increasing order the distance between the flying platforms and their mother flying platform. The algorithm is also applicable to the connections between the medium layer flying platforms and the low layer flying platforms.

Step 2: The second step is to find the final connections for each mother flying platform with its child flying platforms. We consider the connections between flying platforms in the high layer and the medium layer. Firstly, initialize the counters of links as C_L and bandwidth as C_B for each mother flying platform. If a flying platform is in the list of each mother flying platform's child flying platforms S_{Hi} and the counters $C_{Li} < C_{Lmax}$ and $C_{Bi} < C_{Bmax}$, the connection between the two flying platforms in two layers is selected. Then remove the same child flying platform from the lists of other mother flying platform' child flying platform S_H and update the number in the counters of

Algorithm 3.3 : Centralized greedy scheme

Input: $N_H, N_M, N_L, L_H, L_M, C_{L_{Hmax}}, C_{B_{Hmax}}, C_{L_{Mmax}}, C_{B_{Mmax}}, T_{HM}, T_{ML}, T_{max}, B$

Output: R

- 1: Initialize: $CH_L = 0, CH_B = 0, CM_L = 0, CM_B = 0$
- 2: **loop** $i = 1 : N_L$ until find the route
- 3: **loop** $j = 1 : N_M$ until find the route
- 4: **if** $L_{Mij} \sim = 0$ and $CM_{Lij} < C_{L_{Mmax}}$ and $CM_{Bij} < C_{B_{Mmax}}$
- 5: **loop** $k = 1 : N_H$ until find the route
- 6: **if** $L_{Hjk} \sim = 0$ and $CH_{Ljk} < C_{L_{Hmax}}$ and $CH_{Bjk} < C_{B_{Hmax}}$ and $T_{HMjk} + T_{MLij} < T_{max}$
- 7: $R_i = (L_{Mij}[1], L_{Hjk}[1]);$
- 8: $CH_{Ljk} += 1, CH_{Bjk} += B_i, CM_{Lij} += 1, CM_{Bij} += B_i;$
- 9: **end if**
- 10: **end loop**
- 11: **end if**
- 12: **end loop**
- 13: **end loop**

link and bandwidth. The algorithm is the same as the link selection between the medium and the low layer.

Step 3: The third step is to find the route based on the associated links. For each connection requirement between the high layer and the low layer via medium layer, if a connection with two links exists, and the total latency time is lower than the TTL (Time to Live), the connection is chosen and added to the set of final routes.

3.5.2 Centralized greedy scheme

As shown in Algorithm 3.3, in the centralized greedy algorithm, the controller has collected the connection information of all the flying platform in the network, and it can distribute the routes for each connection.

The basic parameters of Algorithm 3.3 are similar to Algorithm 3.2. Firstly, initialize the counters of links as CH_L , CM_L and bandwidth as CH_B , CM_B for each mother flying platform in the high layer and the medium layer. Secondly, for each connection requirement from the source flying platform in the low layer to the destination flying platform in the top layer via the medium layer, we consider the requirement as finding the best link between the medium layer and the low layer in stage one and the best link between the high layer and the medium layer in stage two. So, if there is an available link between the flying platforms in the medium layer and the low layer, and the link and bandwidth counters of the flying platform in the medium layer are lower than the maximum links and bandwidth, check the available links between the selected flying platform in the medium layer and the destination flying platform in the high layer. Thirdly, if there is also an available link between the flying platforms in the high layer and the medium layer, the link and bandwidth counters of the flying platform in the high layer are lower than the maximum links and bandwidth, and the total latency time is lower than the TTL, choose the connection with two links as the final route for this connection requirement and add to the set of final routes. In the end, update the link and bandwidth number in the counters of the two layers.

3.6 Simulation platform

In this work, a simulation platform to support the proposed three-layer airborne network is developed by Matlab. An example of the final link distribution result is shown in Figure 3.6. As shown in the figure, the nodes in high, medium and low layers are displayed as dot, asterisk and circle, respectively. The available links are selected and drawn based on PSets algorithm.

FIGURE 3.6: A three-layer airborne network simulation platform by Matlab

Based on this platform, the three-layer airborne network is described by PSets model. The nodes in three layers and all of their main properties are included.

The proposed link distribution schemes for two hops routing can also be added to the platform to simulate the networks. In current work, the proposed centralized and distributed greedy schemes have been developed. Further, other schemes can also be added to contrast with the current schemes and improve the networks.

The simulation data is collected in the platform and it is able to count and record the performance of networks. Then, it is available to analyse and improve the performance of the network. Moreover, as the basic simulation data is collected, some machine learning tools could be used for further analysis and optimization.

3.7 Simulation results and discussions

The simulation is based on the scenario shown in Figure 3.5 and 3.6. Three layers of the airborne network is deployed. The scope of the flying platform deployment area is $1000\text{m} * 1000\text{m} * 1000\text{m}$ in a 3D zone. The flying platforms in three layers are implemented using Poisson distribution with the same mean parameter as half of the scope, $x/2$, $y/2$ and $z/2$. The location of each flying platform has been known as (x_L, y_L, z_L) . The height ranges of HL, ML, and LL flying platforms are $800 \sim 1000\text{m}$, $400 \sim 700\text{m}$ and $0 \sim 400\text{m}$, respectively. The max links and bandwidth of HL flying platform are set as 30 and 300MHz, respectively.

3.7.1 Influence of medium layer flying platforms number

The flying platforms in the medium layer have been seemed as the relay flying platforms between the high layer and the low layer. So, we consider the influence of flying platform number in the medium layer to the average latency and overall reliability also known as the unassociated ratio of the network. The number of flying platforms in the high layer and the low layer is static and the number of flying platforms in the medium layer increases from 15 to 90. Other essential parameters are defined and shown in Table 3.3. Exclusively, the flying platforms in the medium layer are considered with different performance. These flying platforms have varied random latency range, max connected links number, and max bandwidth. In the simulation, we acquire the average latency and connection unassociated ratio to show the performance of the two proposed schemes.

TABLE 3.3: Simulation parameters of the airborne network

Parameter	Value
location	(x_L, y_L, z_L)
number: HL ML LL	6, [15:15:90], 90
signal cover area: HL ML LL	3000, 1000, 300
scope (m): $x y z$	1000, 1000, 1000
height (m): HL ML LL	800-1000, 400-700, 0-400
max links: HL ML	30, [10, 5, 3]
max bandwidth (MHz): HL ML	300, [50, 30, 20]
real bandwidth (MHz):	5

FIGURE 3.7: Average latency vs. number of medium layer flying platforms.

Figure 3.7 depicts the average latency vs. the number of ML flying platforms. It shows that both of the two PSets based schemes decrease the latency obviously, especially when increasing the number of ML flying platforms. However, the average latency is always similar even increasing the number of ML flying platforms in the traditional shortest path scheme. In the PSets based centralized greedy scheme, the average latency is near to the shortest latency

FIGURE 3.8: Unassociated ratio vs. number of medium layer flying platforms.

in the system (we define it as 5ms) when the number of ML flying platforms is more than 60. It is always near to 5.5ms. In the PSets based distributed greedy scheme, the average latency decrease to about 6.1ms from 7.6ms with the increasing of ML flying platforms number. The performance of the distributed scheme is more unsatisfactory than the centralized scheme because each connection only has the routing information of itself and conflicts with other connections. In contrast, the flying platforms in the centralized greedy scheme have the routing information of all the flying platforms in the network and also able to select the optimized routing for the whole network.

With the limited number of ML flying platforms, the flying platforms in LL cannot always connect to HL via ML. If a LL flying platform cannot connect to HL via ML, it is unassociated. The unassociated ratio is the unassociated LL flying platforms' percentage of all the LL flying platforms. For the ultra

reliability communications, the unassociated ratio should be lower than 0.01% [23], [24]. Otherwise, it could not be able to support the uRLLC. Figure 3.8 plots the unassociated ratio vs. the number of ML flying platforms. In the two types of scheme, the unassociated ratios of PSets based schemes are similar to the traditional shortest path schemes. In the centralized greedy schemes, the unassociated ratio is near to zero when the number of ML flying platforms is more than 30. In the distributed schemes, the unassociated ratio is also decreased with the increasing of ML flying platforms number. When the number of ML flying platforms is more than 45, the unassociated ratio of both distributed schemes is near to 20%. As similar with the performance of average latency, the unassociated ratio of the distributed scheme is poorer than the centralized scheme because the connections can only get the routing information of itself and have to conflict with other connections.

From the simulation result, we can see that the average latency and unassociated ratio are the lowest in the PSets based centralized greedy scheme out of all the schemes. This scheme is satisfactory to support the requirement of uRLLC. However, the unassociated ratio of PSet distributed scheme is performing marginally better than traditional distributed scheme on ultra reliability. Further optimization works should be considered on decreasing the conflict of link connection.

3.7.2 Sensitivity of user bandwidth

Based on the simulation in the previous subsection, we consider the sensitivity of different distributed bandwidth to users on the average latency and unassociated ratio. Each link in the network could support multiple users. The supported number of users depends on the bandwidth of each link and the allocated bandwidth of each user. Based on the result of average latency vs.

FIGURE 3.9: Average latency vs. user bandwidth.

FIGURE 3.10: Unassociated ratio vs. user bandwidth.

number of ML flying platforms and unassociated ratio vs. the number of ML flying platforms, the number of ML flying platforms is set as 60. It satisfies the simulation situation that both the average latency and unassociated ratio of the network are low with a mixed number of ML flying platforms. As shown in Figure 3.9, with the increasing of user's bandwidth, the average latency of traditional distributed scheme also increases. However, the latency of the other schemes is not influenced. Figure 3.10 demonstrate the unassociated ratio vs. the bandwidth of each user. The unassociated ratios of distributed greedy schemes increase with the increase of user's bandwidth. The performance of distributed schemes is decreased in high bandwidth application.

3.7.3 Further potential optimization of PSets parameters by SVM

A primary work to further optimize the parameters of PSets by SVM [55] is simulated in this subsection to support the complex networks. In contrast with the simulations in the previous two subsections, the random latency and the confidence interval of its reliability are added in this simulation. The latency range of links from high to medium layer is set as 1 to 3.9ms, and the latency range of links from medium to low layer is set as 4 to 6.9ms. The satisfied latency is shorter than 10ms. If the sum of two hop latency is longer than 10ms, this link is withdrawn in the link distribution scheme. The confidence intervals of reliability in both links are between 99.9993% and 100%. Currently, the reliabilities of all the links are satisfied to connect in the network, which is set as better than 99.999%. However, it is still divided into three levels by PSets to focus on higher reliability. The other parameters of this simulation are the same as the previous simulation parameters shown in Table 3.2.

FIGURE 3.11: Average latency vs. number of medium layer flying platforms with the optimization by SVM

Figure 3.11 shows the result of SVM based optimization scenario in contrast with the previous PSets based centralized greedy scheme. Due to the significant optimization of performance by PSets, it is near to the best scheme and the optimization of SVM is not so much. The average latency of the optimized scheme by SVM is always near to the previous PSets based scheme. After training by multiple loops, the best classifier model is applied. The current result by SVM is not significant, so it shows that the current PSets based algorithm is already a satisfactory approach to optimize the networks as so far.

3.8 Summary

It is a potential solution to exploit airborne networks to support the uRLLC application for future networks. In this chapter, a PSets based optimized link selection scheme has been proposed for the uRLLC in multiple layers airborne network. Two link distribution schemes have been proposed, namely, the centralized greedy scheme and distributed greedy scheme to optimize the performance of networks. It has been shown that the PSets based scheme can decrease the average latency while the unassociated ratio is moderately better than the traditional schemes. It also shows that the distributed greedy scheme cannot support ultra reliability because of the conflict on link selection. The primary idea to optimize the networks by SVM is also proposed. In future work, the schemes to decrease the conflict on link selection would be considered to improve the associated ratio of the distributed self-organizing network along with the optimization of PSets parameters would also be proposed to support the application in the multi-layer networks.

Chapter 4

Heterogeneous routing for WSNs

4.1 Introduction

Due to the development of 5G communications, the Internet of Things is popular in more application scenes. In the mMTC case of 5G, the wireless sensor nodes connect to the 5G mobile networks directly. However, before the mMTC of 5G is near to apply in the next years, the traditional IoT is still developing based on other protocols and it is possible to integrate into the 5G networks in the future.

Heterogeneous wireless sensor networks (WSNs) have become an area of increased research interest in recent years. Such networks comprise a number of wireless nodes of varying capabilities that employ different wireless protocols. As a result of this variation, network performance can deteriorate when traditional routing protocols are used and bottlenecks can form when linking weak nodes with lower capabilities. In addition, application requirements may

vary across different network contexts, further compounding the challenges facing traditional protocol designs. For these reasons, it is necessary to design a new routing scheme that can dynamically adapt to multiple application requirements and thus avoid bottlenecked nodes. It is proposed that Polychromatic Sets (PSets) theory can be used to create a new network topology model, building a representation that includes multiple metrics of the network in question. In this section, a PSets-based routing discovery scheme is introduced, alongside a PSets-based multi-constrained dynamic routing protocol. Simulation data shows that this protocol predominantly selects high priority nodes for routing, whilst also reducing the use of low priority nodes within the network. In so doing, it is argued that the proposed method significantly increases overall network performance.

The performance requirements of a network differ in various application contexts. For example, in an emergency situation like using a WSN to monitor a forest fire, the primary requirement of this network is that the nodes continue to work for as long as possible - energy saving becomes a key part of extending the lifetime of this network. During the normal monitoring process, most devices could be turned into the sleep mode, with only a few devices left running regularly in order to decrease energy consumption. Then, when the use case changes to detecting fire, the network will now be required to operate with high throughput and reliability. The previous routing scheme used during monitoring will need to be improved to find better routes. Therefore, the routing protocols of such a WSN need to be adapted to become dynamic, to better change from monitoring to an emergency use case.

A heterogeneous sensor network can consist of different sensor nodes, that monitor temperature, humidity, smog sensors and also employ cameras for visual data. These devices may operate differently in terms of frequency, bandwidth, wireless protocol, node energy level and location. It can be measured

taht the performance of such sensors in terms of properties like throughput, delay and packet delivery ratio. In this section, eight network property parameters, namely location, frequency, residual energy, energy consumption, power mode, bandwidth, throughput, and delay, are considered in the design of routing protocols for a heterogeneous WSN based on Polychromatic Sets (PSets) theory. A dynamic route discovery scheme is then designed for these routing protocols.

PSets theory is an extension of graph theory, itself is a common approach used to design networking protocols. Traditionally, only one or two metrics are considered in a graph when a routing protocol is designed. However, in a heterogeneous network, multiple metrics need to be considered. Therefore, it is essential to investigate new types of graph theories to design algorithms and protocols for modern complex heterogeneous networks. It is argued that PSets theory has the ability to consider a larger number of properties as set elements and describe the relations among the properties, which makes it an appropriate tool for the design of efficient networking protocols. Previous research has demonstrated that it may be used to design protocols for large-scale sensor networks. In this chapter, the research is extended to apply to heterogeneous networks, allowing us to investigate the possibility of applying PSets theory to design protocols for more complex networks.

4.2 Network model

A wireless sensor network is a mesh network working in ad hoc mode. With the exception of popular wireless protocols like Wi-Fi and Zigbee, most new Bluetooth protocols now support a mesh topology [5]. At the same time, 5G will also provide more opportunities for WSNs to access the Internet. As

FIGURE 4.1: A heterogeneous wireless sensor network

shown in Figure 4.1, there are multiple wireless sensor nodes with different functions (and performance) based on different protocols. All of these nodes are operating in ad hoc mode, so a more complex heterogeneous network is formed to support a greater number of requirements. Having said this, the design of routing protocols inside heterogeneous networks is becoming more difficult because of the difference in wireless protocols and also the poor communication ability of heterogeneous sensor nodes. The capabilities of sensor nodes in heterogeneous WSNs vary widely, and the performance of links in such networks is also unreliable. As a result, multi-constrained dynamic path selection becomes a closely related problem - it is well-known as an NP-hard problem [56][57].

In this section, a network with many different type of nodes is defined, which is shown in Figure 4.1. These nodes are deployed with multiple protocols, like Wi-Fi, Bluetooth and ZigBee. Each node has different properties, like residual energy, throughput and so on. As shown in Figure 4.2,

eight main parameters of a heterogeneous WSN are considered for designing routing protocols, including location, frequency, node residual energy, energy consumption level, power mode, bandwidth, throughput, and delay.

Location: The location of a node is a popular metric in wireless sensor networks for designing geographical routing protocols. Based on GPS or other localization techniques [58], it is easy for the nodes to acquire the information of their location. A node's location is defined as $L(x_L, y_L, z_L)$ in a three-dimensional plane or $L(x_L, y_L)$ in a two-dimensional plane.

Frequency: In a heterogeneous network, network nodes may be equipped with facilities operating at different frequencies. The nodes can only connect with other nodes operating on the same frequency band and protocol. Some of these nodes are able to operate at multiple frequencies. In this scenario,

FIGURE 4.2: Routing discovery based on different metrics

five popular protocols are considered and defined as: C_a , 5GHz (based on IEEE 802.11ac protocol); C_n , 2.4GHz (based on IEEE 802.11n protocol); C_g , 2.4GHz (based on IEEE 802.11g protocol); C_b , 2.4GHz (based on IEEE 802.11b protocol); and C_z , 2.4GHz (based on IEEE 802.15.4 protocol).

Residual energy: Since most of the sensor nodes are powered by battery, energy consumption is one of the biggest concerns for WSNs. In order to extend the lifetime of the networks, sensor nodes with high residual energy are more often used during data transmission. The low residual energy nodes are protected and used less to conserve energy. In order to meet the requirement of applying set theory in designing protocols, four levels of nodes' residual energy are defined as: R_u , *Unlimited Residual Energy*; R_h , *High Residual Energy*; R_m , *Medium Residual Energy*; and R_l , *Low Residual Energy*.

Energy consumption: The energy consumption of different types of nodes in a heterogeneous network is always different. The energy consumption of nodes is defined using three levels: E_l , *Low Energy Consumption*; E_m , *Medium Energy Consumption*; and E_h , *High Energy Consumption*.

Power mode: In wireless sensor networks, network nodes have four power modes: sending, receiving, idle, and sleep. In some special applications, another mode, silence, is also considered. Transfer time can be minimized by choosing relay nodes working on high priority modes (like idle) over nodes working on low priority modes (like sending). The five parameters of power mode are defined as: S_s , *Sending*; S_r , *Receiving*; S_i , *Idle*; S_p , *Sleep*; and S_l , *Silence*.

Bandwidth: Bandwidth is an important metric to describe the capability of communications in wireless networks. The bandwidth of links connecting various devices is normally different. In heterogeneous networks, the largest

available bandwidth between various devices is defined with three parameters: B_h , *High Bandwidth*; B_m , *Medium Bandwidth*; and B_l , *Low Bandwidth*.

Throughput and delay: The throughput and delay of networks are two important metrics to describe the QoS of wireless networks. In this scenario, the available throughput is defined with three parameters: T_h , *High Throughput*; T_m , *Medium Throughput*; and T_l , *Low Throughput*. The delay of networks is also defined with three parameters: D_l , *Low Delay*; D_m , *Medium Delay*; and D_h , *High Delay*.

In this subsection, eight metrics of a heterogeneous wireless sensor network have been introduced and defined. In the next subsection, the multiple metrics aware heterogeneous network will be defined in PSets theory using these eight metrics.

4.3 Heterogeneous geographical routing

Location based routing [59] is a popular routing scheme for multi-hop networks including heterogeneous WSNs. Data packets are transmitted to destination nodes based on their location rather than their ID or logical address. In this section, location based routing is used in order to illustrate the performance parameters of routing protocols based on PSets theory.

4.3.1 Colour set

In PSets theory, each property is defined as one individual colour. A colour set is defined to include all the individual colours, as

$$F = \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_j, \dots, f_{n_F}\} \quad (4.1)$$

where f_j is an individual colour and n_F is the number of colours defined in F .

In the case of this section, all the colours, excluding locations, are presented as

$$F = \{C_a, C_n, C_g, C_b, C_z, R_u, R_h, R_m, R_l, E_l, E_m, E_h, S_s, S_r, S_i, S_p, S_l, B_h, B_m, B_l, T_h, T_m, T_l, D_l, D_m, D_h\} \quad (4.2)$$

The colours in (5.2) are classified into several groups, as:

$$F \left\{ \begin{array}{l} G_C = \{C_a, C_n, C_g, C_b, C_z\} \\ G_R = \{R_u, R_h, R_m, R_l\} \\ G_E = \{E_l, E_m, E_h\} \\ G_S = \{S_s, S_r, S_i, S_p, S_l\} \\ G_B = \{B_h, B_m, B_l\} \\ G_T = \{T_h, T_m, T_l\} \\ G_D = \{D_l, D_m, D_h\} \end{array} \right. \quad (4.3)$$

In addition, location is utilized for geographical routing, discussed in the next subsection.

Based on the definition of individual colour, the relations of nodes and their colours can be expressed as a matrix:

$$\begin{aligned}
[A \times F] &= \begin{bmatrix} C_g & \cdots & f_j & \cdots & D_h \\ c_{11} & \cdots & c_{1j} & \cdots & c_{1,26} \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \\ c_{i1} & \cdots & c_{ij} & \cdots & c_{i,26} \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \\ c_{n1} & \cdots & c_{nj} & \cdots & c_{n,26} \end{bmatrix} \begin{matrix} a_1 \\ \cdots \\ a_i \\ \cdots \\ a_n \end{matrix} \\
c_{ij} &= \begin{cases} 1, f_j \in F_j \\ 0 \end{cases}
\end{aligned} \tag{4.4}$$

$n_F = 26$ based on the definitions of all the properties.

4.3.2 Greedy forwarding routing

As shown in Figure 4.3, a general location based routing, greedy forwarding routing (GFR) [20][60], is selected for comparison. In traditional GFR, every node broadcasts its location information to its neighbour nodes so that the current node knows the location information of other nodes in its signal coverage area. The location of the destination node is also known.

The area around a node is divided into four zones based on the distance to the destination. As shown in Figure 4.3, the nearest to the destination node is the forwarding area and the other two near areas are neighbour greedy areas and further greedy area, respectively. Whenever a route is to be established, the node in forwarding area which is the nearest to the destination should be selected as the next hop node. If there is no such a suitable node in the forwarding area, the suitable node in neighbour greedy areas should be

FIGURE 4.3: Greedy forwarding routing

selected. The node in further greedy area will be selected as a last resort if necessary.

4.3.3 Next hop selection based on PSets

Route discovery based on PSets theory is different from traditional. As shown in Figure 4.4, when the destination node is not in the signal coverage area of current node, the current node is classified as a node group A_1 by itself and the nodes in the considered area are classified as node group A_2 . After collecting the properties of these nodes in A_2 , the nodes having the expected properties are included in an available paths set. The node which is the nearest to the destination node in this set is selected as the next hop node. In Figure 4.4, node a_3 with high priority property is selected as the next hop node even though node a_2 with low priority in the same area is much nearer to the destination node than node a_3 .

FIGURE 4.4: PSets-based metrics aware next hop node selection

4.3.4 Loop avoidance

FIGURE 4.5: Avoid loop (a)loop problem (b)route discovery (c)final route

In the routing protocol presented above, the problem of a topology loop may appear. As shown in Figure 4.5(a), when a route is discovered from S to D , b is the best relay node of a . However, there are no high priority nodes in the direction from b to D . Therefore, node c is chosen as the relay node following the routing criteria. Node e is the relay node of c and b is the relay node of e . There forms a loop as $b \rightarrow c \rightarrow e \rightarrow b$. In the loop avoiding algorithm, when a relay node is required, it should check the route discovery list to find whether this node is already in the list or not. If this node is

already in the list, it means that a topology loop has been created. So, the next node is labelled as a loop node and the route information on this node is to be deleted. Then another relay node is to be found. As shown in Figure 4.5(b), when a route $b \rightarrow c \rightarrow e \rightarrow b$ has formed a topology loop, node c is labelled in the routing table and the route $c \rightarrow e$ is deleted. Another relay node of b is to be found. Node f is its best relay node. Even though f is a node with low prior property, it is the only available relay node to reach destination node D . A final route is discovered and shown in Figure 4.5(c).

4.4 Simulation and analysis

A platform for simulating heterogeneous wireless sensor networks was developed based on a PSets theory model. In this platform, between 400~1000 nodes are randomly deployed in a $1000m \times 1000m$ area (a map with 400 nodes is shown in Figure 4.2). These nodes have eight different properties (as detailed in Section 4.2) that have been detected for analysis. In the simplified simulation, it is assumed that all nodes can connect with their neighbour nodes which are discovered based on traditional GFR. For energy aware routing, the nodes are assigned different values for three parameters (Residual Energy, Energy Consumption and Power Mode), whilst for QoS aware routing another three parameters (Bandwidth, Throughput and Delay) are employed. The discovery radius of nodes is set as $100\sqrt{2}m$ and the optimized routes are selected based on energy aware routing, QoS aware routing and traditional GFR routing (shown in Figure 4.2).

In the simulations, 100 pairs of source and destination nodes are selected randomly and the application ratios of nodes are calculated based on energy

aware routing, QoS aware routing, metrics selectable routing and traditional GFR routing. The results of these simulations are shown in Figure 4.6 & 4.7.

4.4.1 Application ratio of nodes with different metrics

FIGURE 4.6: Application ratio of nodes with different priority

In current PSets-based routing, the parameters of network metrics are set as different priorities and nodes with high priority metrics are prioritised. The priority of metric parameters is divided into three levels: high priority, medium priority and low priority. Figure 4.6 shows the comparison of different priority nodes between PSets-based routing and traditional GFR. In GFR, the ratios of applying nodes with different priorities are similar, with results between 35% and 45%. This is because different priority nodes are classed as average in this simulation and thus GFR cannot utilize these priorities. In PSets-based routing, the application of nodes with high priority metrics produce results of higher than 60%, and these results improve further as the node numbers increase. The reason for this is that higher node density allows for more candidate nodes with high priority to be chosen. At the same time, few low priority nodes will need to be utilized - no low priority nodes are used when

(a) Different residual energy nodes

(b) Different energy consumption nodes

(c) Different power mode nodes

(d) Different bandwidth nodes

(e) Different throughput nodes

(f) Different delay nodes

FIGURE 4.7: Application of nodes with different properties on different modes

node numbers are greater than 700. Thus, PSets-based routing improves the use of high priority nodes whilst also reducing the use of low priority nodes.

Using PSets-based routing allows different types of multiple metric aware routing to be selected and with different threshold values. In this simulation, the same probability is set for both energy aware and QoS aware selection scenarios with multiple metrics and selectable routing. Figure 4.7 compares three routing scenarios in detail, where 6 metrics are used to determine the ratios of high, medium and low priority nodes. This again shows that PSets-based routing decreases the use of low priority nodes, finally removing them for node numbers greater than 700. For energy aware routing, this improves the lifetime of low residual energy nodes and thus increases the overall lifetime of the network. For QoS aware routing, it improves the quality of network services by increasing the throughput and decreasing the delay with high bandwidth routes. In the multiple metrics aware and selectable routing simulation, the application ratios of low priority nodes are between 10% and 20% - which is half of the ratio of GFR. The application ratios of high and medium priority nodes are more than 80%. It is argued that this shows how PSets-based multiple metrics aware and selectable routing have the flexibility to suit different conditions and requirements and thus improves the performance of the network.

4.4.2 The lifetime of network

A new network is built and the network keeps running until node batteries are depleted. A distribution of between 300 ~ 500 nodes are randomly deployed to simulate and compare the lifetime of this network based on the number of packets being transmitted. The ratio of battery powered nodes (limited energy) and power cable nodes (unlimited energy) is 3:1. The ratio of nodes on different energy consumptions is $c_L : c_M : c_H = 1 : 1 : 1$. In this simulation, the network dies when the packet delivery ratio is lower than 40%. The

FIGURE 4.8: Lifetime ratio of network

network lifetime of GFR with 300 nodes is set as 1. The lifetime of different networks are then compared with a 300 node GFR network (results shown in Figure 4.8). It can be seen that the lifetime of the network extends with increasing numbers of nodes, with the network lifetime of Psets-based energy aware routing improving in contrast to the network based on traditional GFR. When the number of nodes is more than 350, the lifetime of Psets-based routing is about 50 ~ 100% longer than the GFR network.

Figure 4.9 shows the number of dead nodes recorded when the network has died, showing that the number of dead nodes in the Psets-based routing network is lower than GFR network. The number of dead nodes increases rapidly with an increasing number of nodes in the GFR network, from 30 to more than 200, whilst the number of dead nodes in the Psets-based routing network increases slowly and is always smaller than 50 (when the total number of nodes is lower than 500). The Psets-based routing is thus able to balance the

FIGURE 4.9: Number of death node

lifetime of nodes in a network, where only a few nodes need to be replenished to recover the network.

4.4.3 Overhead

As shown in Figure 4.10, the network overhead is evaluated based on the average hops per route. It is noted that the average number of hops for both Psets-based routing and GFR are positively correlated. In addition, the average hops of Psets-based routing are greater than GFR, though no more than 1 hop. This means that only a part of the Psets-based routing routes has more hops than GFR routes, whilst the other routes have the same number of hops. Some routes based on Psets-based routing do have more than one hop, though this is because the selected route includes more distant nodes in order to bypass the low energy nodes - even though the low energy level nodes

FIGURE 4.10: Overhead (based on the average hops)

route (high energy consumption or low residual energy) is short. Therefore, we argue that the increased cost is beneficial in extending the lifetime of the whole network by decreasing the use of low energy level nodes. At the same time, based on these simulation results the lifetime of the network is increased and the number of dead nodes is decreased.

4.4.4 Throughput and delay

200 pairs of random routes were selected to analyse the throughput and delay of network. Figure 4.11 shows that the average throughput of GFR networks is limited to 8Mbps, because the bandwidth of some nodes in the simulated networks is 11Mbps (based on the IEEE 802.11b protocol). However, PSets-based routing is able to avoid applying these nodes with low bandwidth and thus

FIGURE 4.11: Average throughput

FIGURE 4.12: Average delay

improve the overall throughput of network. Again it is noted that for PSets-based routing a larger number of nodes will also increase network throughput. Figure 4.12 shows how PSets-based routing discovery can choose lower delay links, thus decreasing network delay (again this decreases further as the node numbers increase). Overall, GFR network delay is always higher than PSets-based routing. We propose that PSets-based routing increases the throughput and decreases the delay of network effectively, thus improving the QoS of the network involved.

4.5 Summary

In this chapter, a application scene of routing optimization is proposed for the routing optimization of large-scale heterogeneous WSNs, a multi-constrained dynamic route discovery scheme based on PSets theory is proposed. It is argued that multiple metrics jointly influence the performance of heterogeneous WSNs, and so a multiple metrics aware dynamic routing protocol will be more efficient in enhancing the capacity of these networks. A PSets-based routing protocol was designed to improve the performance of networks by considering multiple metrics of heterogeneous networks together. Results show that the performance of heterogeneous networks is significantly improved based on this method. It is suggested that this demonstrates the feasibility of applying PSets theory for designing efficient and high quality routing protocols for complex heterogeneous networks.

Chapter 5

Service oriented routing for IoT

5.1 Introduction

Due to the development of 5G communications, the Internet of Things is popular in more application scenes. In the mMTC case of 5G, the wireless sensor nodes connect to the 5G mobile networks directly. However, before the mMTC of 5G is near to apply in the next years, the traditional IoT is still developing based on other protocols and it is possible to integrate into the 5G networks in the future. Internet of Things (IoT) is being developed rapidly and applied widely in our society. A large number of network nodes with different attributes join in the network and makes the structure of the network rather complex. Traditional research about network routing concentrates on a few network attributes as routing metrics like energy and bandwidth. However, the network performance may be decreased when concentrating on one or few metrics. In this section, a service oriented routing is proposed based on Polychromatic Sets theory. A scheme of cross-layer design and virtual nodes is

applied to improve the network performance. Therefore, the network performance could be balanced on multiple metrics based on the different requirements of application. The simulation results on NS-3 prove that the scheme is effectively able to improve the performance of network when considering multiple network metrics.

Internet of Things (IoT) is more than popular in modern communication networks. The Quality of Service (QoS) is an significant concern for the performance of IoT systems [61][62]. Normally, an IoT system consists of multiple types of network nodes, and, therefore, named as a heterogeneous network. The properties and performance of these nodes are always different, and the requirement of QoS is also different [63][64].

In order to integrate and interoperate these IoT devices and guarantee the QoS requirements, Service Oriented Architecture (SOA) provides a promising solution [65]. SOA is different from traditional networks that solve the node-to-node communications based on IP packets, information and services are the centric of SOA [66]. Therefore, the network architecture becomes more complex. In order to guarantee the performance, cross-layer design and virtual network are two typical methods to improve the SOA-based complex networks [67].

PSets theory is a compositive set method to consider the multiple metrics of network conveniently and then optimize the route discovery of networks by several extended algorithms. In this section, the multiple metrics of network in different layers are considered together by PSets based on previous work. Then the load of network is distributed to multiple concurrent requirements in a virtual network.

5.2 Network model

Cross-layer design is widely applied on the optimization of networks. The ability of hardware on physical layer significantly influences the performance of network layer, and the requirements on application layer also depend heavily on the performance of network layer. Therefore, it is important to optimize the network routing by considering the requirements based on multiple layers. For service oriented networks, the route discovery of network layer generally considers the service requirements of application layer and transport layer. At the same time, the performance of network interface layer is also considered by route discovery to choose a better route to improve QoS. Cross-layer analysis is an important feature and an improved problem in SOA [61]. In cross-layer networks, a software layer based on middleware technology is added as the interface of two layers to solve the interconnectivity of the cross-layer problem [68].

Network virtualization is a significant feature in service oriented networks. The traditional networks always solve the data transmission problem between node and node. However, the data transmission is not limited to one route in a service oriented network. Multiple routes could be built to transmit one data file. Then, the service oriented network is regarded as a virtual network. The data flow of a data file is not the same as the packet flow of one route any more. The optimization of interface and interconnectivity between virtual network and physical network needs to be solved in service oriented networks [62][69].

In this section, by applying a cross-layer design approach, different metrics of the network are collected and considered together. Then Polychromatic Sets (PSets) theory is used to integrate the multiple dynamic metrics and virtual network is used to distribute the network for multiple services. The optimized

routing by considering QoS would be discovered based on the multiple metrics integrated by PSets.

FIGURE 5.1: A lightweight service oriented architecture

In this section, a SOA-based lightweight network structure is proposed. As shown in Figure 5.1, the computer network is abstracted as three layers: service layer, network layer and network interface layer. The service layer includes the application layer and transport layer in traditional TCP/IP model. As it is different from other research work which a new layer is added to describe the service requirements of network, we integrate all the acquired service requirements to network layer based on previous work. At the same

time, the performance of devices on network interface layer is also integrated in network layer.

PSets is used to collect the acquired metrics after acquiring the service requirements and performance of network devices before starting the route discovery. Then an optimized routing algorithm is chosen to provide data transmission service based on the PSets-based Multi-constraint Fast Routing Selection Algorithm. The service distribution scenario is configured previously for special service requirement and performance of network devices. Details of the routing scenario are introduced in next subsection.

There are two ways to acquire the service requirements or performance of network devices: active sensing and passive acquiring. Active sensing is to sense the data flow or packet flow and acquire the performance based on the throughput and header information of packets, and then compare with the pre-configured threshold value to determine the level of performance. Passive acquiring is to transmit the parameters of performance to network layer directly from service layer or network interface layer. The passive way is much easier and more accurate, but there are some more work needed to be done at service layer and network interface layer.

5.3 Service oriented routing

Based on PSets theory, it is convenient to integrate the complex network nodes and their properties, the service requirements on service layer and the device performance on network interface layer together. Then, the property parameters are considered by the PSets-based Multi-constraint Fast Routing Selection Algorithm and the route discovery scheme is implemented to optimize the performance of the network.

5.3.1 Dynamic virtual nodes

FIGURE 5.2: Nodes in the physical network and virtual network

The physical network nodes are normally defined in traditional networks. In this work, a dynamic virtual network is also defined. In virtual networks, a physical network node is considered as multiple virtual nodes and provides multiple different services. One data file can also be transmitted through multiple routes based on the service requirements. Therefore, the dynamic virtual nodes are defined. As shown in Figure 5.2, the set of all the physical nodes GA_p is defined as:

$$GA_p = \{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n\} \quad (5.1)$$

where n is the number of physical nodes.

The set of all the virtual nodes GA_v is defined as:

$$GA_v = \{\{a_1, a_2, a_3\}, \{a_4, a_5\}, \{a_3, a_6, a_7\}, \dots, \{a_{m-1}, a_m\}\} \quad (5.2)$$

where a is a virtual node and m is the number of virtual nodes, and

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} A_1 = \{a_1, a_2, a_3\} \\ A_2 = \{a_4, a_5\} \\ A_3 = \{a_3, a_6, a_7\} \\ \dots \\ A_n = \{a_{m-1}, a_m\} \end{array} \right. \quad (5.3)$$

where $a_3 \subset \{A_1, A_3\}$. There is a special link between node A_1 and A_3 to provide packet transmission service for a_3 . So $a_3 \subset \{A_1, A_3\}$ is defined as link $L_{a_3} = \{A_1, A_3\}$.

5.3.2 Service requirements and physical performance

In an IoT system, different services have different requirements. Based on the passive acquiring and active sensing of service requirements introduced in last section, the typical service types include interactive, bulk, real-time, normal, narrow-band and undefined. As shown in Table 5.1, the service requirements on capacity, jitter, delay and packet loss are listed and the priority is also given based on the experience of analysis on network requirements. The priority of service requirements can also be changed dynamically.

At the same time, there are also some other physical network properties related to the performance of network. These properties are effective for balancing the overhead and load of networks, and improving the QoS of network.

TABLE 5.1: Service requirements of IoT

Flow Type	Capacity	Jitter	Delay	Packet loss
Interactive	High	High	High	High
Bulk	High	Low	Low	Low
Real-time	Medium	High	High	High
Normal	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium
Narrow-band	Low	Low	Low	Low
Undefined	-	-	-	-

Therefore, the performance of physical devices is also considered and added to the set of service requirements and physical performances in the SOA-based cross-layer design. The typical physical network properties includes:

Energy. Green wireless network is proposed to save the energy and protect the environment. In the meantime, part of the nodes in IoT systems are powered by battery and the energy is limited. Therefore, the energy consumption in routing and the residual energy of nodes are considered in this work.

Radio Frequency, Connectivity and Interference. In complex heterogeneous networks, different physical devices in a network are applied based on different protocols on network interface layer, like WiFi and Zigbee, and some devices are able to work on different radio frequency. Therefore, the radio frequency, connectivity and interference of links are significant factors for the network performance and they are considered in this work.

Activity of Nodes. Normally, the networks can work on sending, receiving, idle and sleep mode. The serious packet impact might happen if a new connection is established between the nodes working on either sending or receiving mode. It would spend longer time if the node is in sleep mode and has to be awoken. Therefore, the mode of nodes is also considered in this work.

Based on the service requirements and physical node performance introduced above, the basic network properties could be defined by PSets theory.

The set of property types $GF(GA)$ is defined as:

$$GF(GA) = \{GF_1, GF_2, \dots, GF_l\} \quad (5.4)$$

The parameters of one property is defined as a set GF :

$$\begin{cases} GF_1 = \{f_1, f_2, f_3\} \\ GF_2 = \{f_4, f_5, f_6\} \\ \dots \\ GF_l = \{f_{k-1}, f_k\} \end{cases} \quad (5.5)$$

where l is the number of properties and k is the number of the parameters of the total properties.

Therefore, the parameter set of the total properties $GF_f(GA)$ is:

$$GF_f(GA) = \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_k\} \quad (5.6)$$

5.3.3 Network described by PSets

The total nodes and the parameters of their properties are described by a matrix as:

$$\begin{aligned}
[GA_v \times GF_f(GA_v)] &= \begin{bmatrix} & f_1 & \cdots & f_j & \cdots & f_k \\ c_{11} & \cdots & c_{1j} & \cdots & c_{1k} & \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \\ c_{i1} & \cdots & c_{ij} & \cdots & c_{ik} & \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \\ c_{m1} & \cdots & c_{mj} & \cdots & c_{mk} & \end{bmatrix} \begin{matrix} a_1 \\ \cdots \\ a_i \\ \cdots \\ a_m \end{matrix} & \quad (5.7) \\
c_{ij} &= \begin{cases} 1, f_j \in GF_j(A_{ai}) \\ 0 \end{cases}
\end{aligned}$$

If the property parameter of one node a_i is set as f_j , the element c_{ij} in matrix (5.11) is set as 1; otherwise, it is set as 0.

5.3.4 Routing scheme

The PSets-based Multi-constraint Fast Routing Selection Algorithm (PM-FRS) is proposed and presented in this section. Based on the node properties and network properties which have been defined in last section, the optimized network topology could be quickly selected for different requirements of network service, and then discover the routing based on the selected network topology. First of all, several sets of properties are defined as:

$$\begin{cases} S_{F_1} = \{f_1, f_4, f_6\} \\ S_{F_2} = \{f_2, f_3, f_4\} \\ \cdots \\ S_{F_n} = \{f_{k_{k_1}}, f_{k_2}\} \end{cases} \quad (5.8)$$

The property sets are sorted based on different priorities in different situations. For example, the priority is $S_{F_1} > S_{F_2} > \dots > S_{F_n}$ in situation 1, and the priority is $S_{F_n} > \dots > S_{F_2} > S_{F_1}$ in situation 2.

When the required set of property is S_{F_1} , the corresponding nodes and the set of properties are defined as:

$$[G_A \times S_{F_1}(G_A)] = \begin{matrix} & f_1 & \cdots & f_j & \cdots & f_k & \\ \left[\begin{array}{cccccc} c_{11} & \cdots & c_{1j} & \cdots & c_{1k} & \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \\ c_{i1} & \cdots & c_{ij} & \cdots & c_{ik} & \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \\ c_{m1} & \cdots & c_{mj} & \cdots & c_{mk} & \end{array} \right] & \begin{array}{l} a_1 \\ \cdots \\ a_i \\ \cdots \\ a_m \end{array} \end{matrix} \quad (5.9)$$

$$c_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, f_j \in G_A(A_{a_i}) \\ 0 \end{cases}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \forall \{f_{j_1}, \dots, f_{j_2}\} \subset GF_l, \\ f_{j_1} \wedge \dots \wedge f_{j_2} = 1 \end{aligned} \quad (5.10)$$

For any property type GF_l , at least one property in S_{F_1} should be *True*.

The PSets-based Multi-constraint Fast Routing Selection Algorithm is shown in Algorithm 5.1. The matrix of properties in set S_{F_n} and the corresponding nodes are quickly selected based on the selection algorithm. Then, the new network topology is built based on the selected nodes.

Algorithm 5.1 : PMFRS Algorithm

Input: $S_{F_1}, [GA_v \times GF_f(GA_v), GF(GA), k, m]$
Output: $[G_A \times S_{F_1}(G_A)]$

- 1: Initialize;
- 2: num_row = size(GA_v);
- 3: num_column = size(S_{F_1});
- 4: $[G_A \times S_{F_1}(G_A)] = \text{zero}(\text{num_row}, \text{num_column});$
- 5: **do**
- 6: **if** $f_j == f_{j_{S_{F_1}}}$
- 7: $[G_A \times S_{F_1}(G_A)] <== f_j;$
- 8: **while** $j < k$
- 9: **do**
- 10: **if** $!(f_{j_1}, \dots, f_{j_2} \subset GF_l \ \& \ f_{j_1} \wedge \dots \wedge f_{j_2} == 1)$
- 11: delete row(i);
- 12: **while** $i < m$

AODV is a typical routing protocol applied on wireless ad hoc networks. Based on the network topology selected by the PSets-based algorithm, the extended AODV routing is used to discover the routes in this work. In addition, the PSets theory has been used in location based routing in our previous work.

5.4 Simulation and analysis

The simulation is done on NS-3. AODV is a pre-positioned routing for wireless ad hoc network in NS-3. The simulation of this work extends the existing AODV routing in NS-3. In addition, a simulation of SOA for wireless ad hoc network is proposed in paper [70], and the simulation of this work is also based on that one.

In this section, two types of wireless nodes with different performance on services are applied. The ratio of each type of node is 50%. Based on traditional AODV routing, these nodes are applied randomly and the performance

FIGURE 5.3: Performance of delay with different number of nodes

FIGURE 5.4: Delay on different nodes distance

of these nodes are not considered. However, by applying the PSets-based routing, the high priority nodes are collected based on the requirements, and then these nodes are selected by the PMFRS algorithm. The new network topology is built based on the selected nodes and then PMFRS algorithm is applied for route discovery.

5.4.1 Delay

As shown in Figure 5.3, the delay of network communication is shown for the networks with 10 100 random nodes, and the distance between every two nodes is 50m. By traditional AODV routing, it cannot discover the routes before overtime when the number of nodes is more than 50 in a network. When 10 50 nodes are deployed in the network, the delay increases from 3ms to 24ms rapidly. However the delay by applying the PMFRS algorithm is much lower than the traditional AODV routing , where the delay only increases from 1ms to 8ms. When the number of nodes in the network is more than 50, the network is still available to discover routes effectively. The delay is increased from 9ms to 16ms when the number of nodes increases to 100 from 50.

The PSets-based routing protocol can also improve the performance of network effectively when considering different distance between nodes when the number of nodes is fixed. In this simulation, 30 nodes are deployed in a network. As shown in Figure 5.4, the delay in the network applying traditional AODV routing increases from 1ms to about 11ms when the nodes distance ranges from 10m to 50m. However, the delay is increased only from nearly 0 to 4ms with the same distance by applying the PSets-based routing. The delay decreases more than half in comparing with the traditional AODV routing. The PSets-based routing is possible to improve the performance of QoS effectively.

FIGURE 5.5: Energy consumption based on time

FIGURE 5.6: Energy consumption on different packet sizes

5.4.2 Energy consumption

The PMFRS-based routing protocol can also save energy when considering the energy consumption. As shown in Figure 5.5, the energy consumption increases linearly following the time. The energy consumption of data transmission is a little more than 1W in traditional AODV routing. However, the energy consumption is less than 1W by PMFRS-based routing. In contrast with the traditional AODV routing, the new routing is able to choose the energy saving nodes and routes, therefore, the energy consumption is decreased obviously.

A number of nodes are high energy consumption nodes in this simulation, therefore, the energy consumption in unit time increases obviously following the increasing of data packet size. As shown in Figure 5.6, some high energy consumption nodes are applied based on traditional AODV routing. With the increasing of packet size from 100 bytes to 1000 bytes, the average energy consumption in unit time increases from about 6J to 9.5J. However, the energy consumption does not increase based on the PMFRS-based routing. Due to the new routing scheme decreasing the application of high energy consumption nodes effectively and most of the transmission nodes are low energy consumption nodes, the average energy consumption in unit time is always about 5J. The new routing is widely applicative in the network with different packet sizes.

5.5 Summary

In this chapter, a application scene of routing optimization is proposed for the cross-layer routing optimization of service-oriented IoT, a SOA-based routing scheme is proposed. This scheme is applicable for complex heterogeneous

IoT systems. Cross-layer analysis and virtual networking are applied in the analysis of network, and then PSets is used to define the properties of virtual nodes and network. An extended dynamic AODV routing protocol for wireless virtual network is designed to test and verify the performance of the network in simulation. The simulation results show that the performance of network is improved in comparing with the traditional AODV routing protocol. This scheme provides a helpful idea for improving the service performance of IoT.

Chapter 6

Conclusions

6.1 Summary of achievements

In this thesis, the modelling and optimization of complex communication networks are detailed explained based on Polychromatic Sets theory. The PSets theory and its application in complex networks are presented. Several network scenes are defined and optimized by the PSets model.

It is a potential solution to exploit airborne networks to support the uRLLC application for future networks. In this thesis, a PSets based optimized link selection scheme has been proposed for the uRLLC in multiple layers airborne network. Two link distribution schemes have been proposed, namely, the centralized greedy scheme and distributed greedy scheme to optimize the performance of networks. It has been shown that the PSets based scheme can decrease the average latency while the unassociated ratio is moderately better than the traditional schemes. It also shows that the distributed greedy scheme cannot support ultra reliability because of the conflict on link selection. In future work, the schemes to decrease the conflict on link selection

would be considered to improve the associated ratio of the distributed self-organizing network along with the optimization of PSets parameters would also be proposed to support the application in the multi-layer networks.

Furthermore, a multi-constrained dynamic route discovery scheme for heterogeneous wireless sensor networks and an SOA-based routing scheme for IoT are proposed based on PSets theory in this thesis.

In the multi-constrained dynamic route discovery scheme for heterogeneous WSNs. We argue that multiple metrics jointly influence the performance of heterogeneous WSNs, and so a multiple metrics aware dynamic routing protocol will be more efficient in enhancing the capacity of these networks. A PSets-based routing protocol was designed to improve the performance of networks by considering multiple metrics of heterogeneous networks together. Results show that the performance of heterogeneous networks is significantly improved based on this method. We suggest that this demonstrates the feasibility of applying PSets theory for designing efficient and high-quality routing protocols for complex heterogeneous networks.

The SOA-based routing scheme is applicable for complex heterogeneous IoT systems. Cross-layer analysis and virtual networking are applied in the analysis of the network, and then PSets is used to define the properties of virtual nodes and network. An extended dynamic AODV routing protocol for the wireless virtual network is designed to test and verify the performance of the network in simulation. The simulation results show that the performance of the network is improved in comparing with the traditional AODV routing protocol. This scheme provides a helpful idea for improving the service performance of IoT.

6.2 Future directions

6.2.1 Optimization of 5G networks based on AI

Artificial intelligence (AI) is possible to analyse and optimise the networks under the background of beyond 5G era [71][72]. In the further research, the optimization of network routing will be considered based on suitable AI algorithms in the PSets model.

6.2.2 Development and application of AIoT platform

Based on the current outputs in this thesis, the proposed IoT scheme is possible to be applied in industry based on PSets model. The first step is to apply the routing optimization scheme in the unauthorized license networks. And then converge the unauthorized license networks and 5G mobile networks with the evolution of 5G and B5G networks.

6.2.3 Further modelling and application of complex networks

In this thesis, a common modelling method for complex communication networks is proposed based on PSets theory. In the future works, the new complex network models will be explored and extended based on the current outputs to optimise and service the networks.

Appendix A

Source Code of PSets

The core source code of PSets has been developed and published online. In this appendix, the basic architecture of PSets and the main Functions are listed.

A.1 Program architecture

As shown in Figure A.1, the architecture of PSets program is displayed. Four main Functions and two assistant Functions are developed in the core program.

PSet_Creat() is used to create a basic set group (PSets) including the set of nodes, set of properties and the matrix of nodes and properties.

PSet_Set_to_AFa() is used to transfer an initialized PSets to an individual colour matrix of a node group.

PSet_AFa_to_AFA() is used to transfer an individual colour matrix to a unified colour matrix of a node group.

FIGURE A.1: Program architecture of PSets core source code

PSet_AFA_to_AAF() is the Function of PSets-based link fast selection algorithm to find the links following the required properties.

The detailed introduction of the PSets theory is in chapter 3 of the thesis.

Other two assistant functions are used to support the arrays' logical operation of **AND** and **OR**.

A.2 Main Functions of PSets

A.2.1 Creat a Set

```
% =====
% Creat a Set
% Function: PSet_Creat(m,n,'name')
% m: Property Number
% n: Element Number
% Attention: Modify the data in 'name'_Set.mat after creation

PSet_Creat(7,12,'test');
```

A.2.2 $[A \times F(a)]$

```
% =====
% Transfer from a Set to  $[A \times F(a)]$ 
% Function: PSet_Set_to_AFa('Set name','AFa name')
% Attention: Modify the element code in 'name'_Element.mat and property code
% in 'name'_Property.mat after creation

PSet_Creat(5,10,'testAFa');
PSet_Set_to_AFa('test','testAFa');
```

A.2.3 $[A \times F(a)]$ to $[A \times F(A)]$

```

% =====
% Transfer from [A X F(a)] to [A X F(A)]
% Function: PSet_AFa_to_AFA('AFa name', 'AFA name')
% Attention: Modify the property code in 'name'_Property.mat after creation,
% the element codes are same with AFa's

PSet_Creat(4,10,'testAFAA'); % The file name is not case sensitive!!!
% copy the element code from AFa_Element to AFAA_Element
n = 10; % number of elements
load testAFa_Element
load testAFAA_Element
for i = 1:n
    testAFAA_Element(1,i) = testAFa_Element(1,i);
end
save('testAFAA_Element.mat', 'testAFAA_Element');

PSet_AFa_to_AFA('testAFa', 'testAFAA');

```

A.2.4 $[A \times F(A)]$ to $[A \times A(F)]$

```

% =====
% Transfer from [A X F(A)] to [A X A(F)]
% Function: PSet_AFA_to_AAF(Element_Group, Property_Group, 'AAF_data_name',
% 'AAF_result_name')
% Struct: Element_Group, Property_Group

PSet_Creat(7,12,'AAF_testdata');

% Define Element Group and Property Group (by sequence!!!)
Element_Group.number = 3;
Element_Group.Group1 = [1,2,3,4,5];
Element_Group.Group2 = [6,7,8,9,10,11];
Element_Group.Group3 = [12];

Property_Group.number = 2;
Property_Group.Group1 = [1,2,3,4,5];
Property_Group.Group2 = [6,7];

PSet_AFA_to_AAF(Element_Group, Property_Group, 'AAF_testdata', 'AAF_testresult');

```

A.2.5 AND and OR

```
% =====  
% And  
% Function: PSet_And(PSet_And_A, PSet_And_B)
```

```
PSet_And_A = [1,0,0,0,1,0];  
PSet_And_B = [0,0,1,0,1,1];  
PSet_And_C = PSet_And(PSet_And_A, PSet_And_B)
```

```
% =====  
% Or  
% Function: PSet_Or(PSet_Or_A, PSet_Or_B)
```

```
PSet_Or_A = [1,0,0,0,1,0];  
PSet_Or_B = [0,0,1,0,1,1];  
PSet_Or_C = PSet_Or(PSet_Or_A, PSet_Or_B)
```

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